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**ACCOMPLISHMENT OF INTERORGANIZATIONAL COLLABORATION: AN
ETHNOMETHODOLOGICAL STUDY OF THE COMMUNICATIVE PRACTICES OF
AN INTERNATIONAL BODY**

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15 August 2023

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Acceptance Page:

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Biographical Sketch

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In 2016, Ms. Bravo took and passed the Environmental Planner licensure examination. Her previous work at Palafox Associates enabled her to gain experience in projects involving comprehensive land use planning of towns and cities, as well as tourism planning of destinations in the Philippines. Prior to becoming an Environmental Planner, she managed the firm's communication team and was involved in developing its social media and website content, creating storylines that complement plans and designs for both the built and natural environments, and organizing thought leadership events in architecture and urban planning, among others.

Ms. Bravo graduated with a degree in BA Organizational Communication in the University of the Philippines Manila in 2008.

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It is with deepest gratitude that I thank the people who have been instrumental in getting me at this point. I am truly grateful for all the support and encouragement that came my way.

First of all, I would like to thank my family for their unconditional support despite me not telling them that I am pursuing a Master of Development Communication degree. They will eventually find that out through this thesis. While I kept this journey mostly to myself, I appreciate my family for giving me space to do what I needed to do without question nor judgement.

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Dedication

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Abstract

ACCOMPLISHMENT OF INTERORGANIZATIONAL COLLABORATION: AN ETHNOMETHODOLOGICAL STUDY OF THE COMMUNICATIVE PRACTICES OF AN INTERNATIONAL BODY

This study looks into the communicative practices of an international body in the accomplishment of interorganizational collaboration or IOC. It aligns with the Montreal School of the communicative constitution of organization or CCO approach, wherein conversations reflect the collective experience of individual members and become authored into text that shapes the collective organization. An ethnomethodological approach was used in carrying out the data collection and analysis. This includes transcribing and coding conversations from meeting workshops of a consortium established by the Southeast Asian Regional Center for Graduate Study and Research in Agriculture (SEARCA).

Results from this study show that contextualizing, consensus building, and confirming commitment (3Cs) are accomplished through communicative practices. These 3Cs constitute IOC through co-orientation and formation of authoritative text. The 3Cs demonstrate an authoritative text that enables individual members of an interorganizational network to act in consonance as a collective organization. This study also explains how the 3Cs could help gain a better appreciation for communication as well as recommendations for future research.

Keywords: interorganizational collaboration; communicative constitution of organization; Southeast Asia

Chapter I

RATIONALE

Interorganizational Collaboration and International Bodies

As the world continues to face challenges with increasing complexity (Widmer et al, 2015) and society will likely experience disruption in waves (Brodie, 2019), collaboration on an international scale becomes necessary in meeting global demands in various sectors including education, health, and trade, among others (Widmer et al, 2015). Through interorganizational collaboration or IOC, the delivery of services can be more efficient by sharing resources and costs; more complex activities can be done through combined efforts; risks and uncertainties may be minimized; as well as gaining knowledge of the local context and building trust with the beneficiaries of an initiative can be done easier, among others (Lundstrom, 2011).

IOC has been defined as a relationship between organizations that cooperate with each other in order to achieve a goal through shared resources (Koschmann and Isbell, 2009). Koschmann further differentiates IOC from other interorganizational relationships like business-supplier relationships and legitimate authority-based partnerships by describing IOCs as more decentralized or less hierarchical, more informal, and more mutual in terms of the exchange of resources.

Interorganizational collaboration involves two or more organizations that are 'legally independent' and 'interdependent with respect to a particular problem domain' (Schrujjer, 2020). Additionally, an institutional definition of IOC implies that participating organizations form an agreement to establish an entirely new institution (Sowa, 2008 as cited in Ada, 2013) with 'shared norms and agreed-upon rules and standards of action between the organizations working together' (Scott, 1995 as cited

in Ada, 2013). Aside from the macro level, Schruijer acknowledges that collaboration also happens at the interindividual level since individuals represent their respective organizations and their interests.

Schruijer (2020) also describes IOC in terms of relational processes. It is where relationships are formed, along with the development of trust and exploring identities and interdependencies to the process of collaboration, among others. IOC also involves roles or “well-defined relationships” (Kozuch and Sienkiewicz-Maly Jurek, 2016).

In terms of resources shared by organizations, Greer (2017) identifies experience, time, and expertise as resources shared by individuals and organizations in a collaborative relationship. She also adds knowledge, effort, and commitment as resources that constitute the process of collaboration. Following Koschmann and Isbell’s earlier definition of IOC, resources are shared to accomplish a goal or goals that will otherwise be difficult or impossible for only one organization to realize.

Lastly, an IOC has a goal to attain or a problem to solve. According to Schruijer (2020), interorganizational collaboration “implies jointly defining a problem domain and from there developing a joint goal—a goal that also is expected to serve the stakeholders’ individual interests.” Aside from problem-solving, other reasons for organizations to collaborate include ‘service integration, attitude or behavior changes, strategic partnerships, problem-solving, planning, political action, or social change’ (Mizrahi et al., 2013 as cited in Greer, 2017).

SEARCA as an International Body

This study aims to add to the existing body of knowledge by giving a communicative explanation to IOC in the context of an international body. It looks into

interorganizational collaboration through the Southeast Asian Regional Center for Graduate Study and Research in Agriculture (SEARCA) as one of the regional centers under a chartered international organization, which is the Southeast Asian Ministers of Education Organization (SEAMEO). SEAMEO SEARCA is both founder and member of a consortium for graduate education in agriculture and natural resources, wherein it regularly collaborates with higher education institutions within Southeast Asia and beyond.

SEARCA is part of an interorganizational network through a consortium it established, which is composed of higher education institutions in Southeast Asia and beyond. This interorganizational network regularly collaborates on grants, knowledge sharing events, capacity building activities, and research in graduate education for agriculture, environment, and natural resources, among others.

My role in the study

My role as a researcher in this study is that of an observer. While I am part of SEARCA or the international body, I cannot claim to be a participant of the interorganizational network since I do not directly serve the Consortium nor represent its member institutions. However, being a SEARCA staff gives me access to the organization and some level of familiarity with the people involved and the activities of the Consortium.

On the other hand, not being a direct participant in the activities of the Consortium and its Secretariat, could mean that I do not have enough understanding of its context. As such, I interviewed members of the Secretariat from time to time in order to validate information, among others. I also requested their assistance in accessing information that could provide me with additional background. However, I

did not discuss with the Secretariat or members of the Consortium any observations and results in order to maintain my own understanding and experience.

Importance of the Study

Studies on the different aspects of collaboration between organizations or IOC continue to gain ground over the years. Earlier studies on interorganizational collaboration could be summarized according to three (3) areas of interest: preconditions, processes, and outcomes (Gray & Wood, 1991 as cited by Ada, 2013). These studies focus on antecedent factors, procedural aspects, and results from or effectivity of a collaboration. IOC studies would later on consider the social and relational characteristics of collaboration, which inspired further studies related to action learning, leadership, emotional dynamics, and discursive practices, among others (Schruijer, 2020).

While these definitions and studies provide insight into the nature of IOC and what it does, they lack an explanation of IOC as a communication phenomenon. Koschmann and Isbell (2019) argue that “organizational communication processes are central to the development and maintenance of IOCs”. IOC involves social interactions, wherein continuing dialogue allows for symbolic interpretations that lead to collective action (Ring and van de Ven 1994, as cited by Koschmann and Isbell, 2009). Hardy et al. (1998) echo Ring and van de Ven’s notion stating that “collective action is generated by conversational activity and content that produce shared meaning.”

Koschmann and Isbell (2019) further suggested to look into the constitutive view of communication as one way of understanding how dialogues or interactions between actors in IOCs create and recreate the collective organization. The

communicative constitution of organization or CCO is described as a collection of perspectives that seeks to describe the role of communication in the nature and existence of organization (Putnam and Nicotera, 2010 as cited in Basque, 2022). While CCO is linked to various approaches or schools of thought, it primarily views communication as an organizing force.

Because of the particular interest of this study in the constitutive role of communication in IOC, an ethnomethodological approach was used in carrying out the data collection and analysis. Ethnomethodology looks into the relationship between the members of the organization and its documents or records (Trace, 2016). In the context of organizations, the convergence between ethnomethodology and the constitutive view of communication lies in the notion “that people at work share and follow routines that make it possible for them to understand their work” (Miranda, 2019). This study aims to gain an understanding of IOC through such routines, specifically communicative practices, which enable members of different institutions to create meaning and act as a collective organization.

Chapter II

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

This chapter explores various aspects of interorganizational collaboration or IOC that explains it as a communication phenomenon. It looks into previous literature on IOC research, including frameworks and methodologies used. It also includes literature that provides insights on collaboration in Southeast Asia in order to better understand the nature of IOC in a similar context to the setting of this study.

Early stages of IOC literature

Various definitions of interorganizational collaboration exist, such that it is possible to identify common themes like: 1. Involvement of two or more organizations, 2. Relationship, 3. Shared resources, and 4. Addressing a common issue or achieving a goal. An example of this is the definition by Koschmann and Isbell (2009) wherein they described IOCs as “cooperative relationships that develop between organizations to leverage resources and solve problems beyond the scope of any single organization.”

Nguyen (2012) also summarized a comprehensive list of scholarly definitions of IOC, as shown in Table 1.

Table 1.

Summary of Various Scholars' Definition of IOC

Scholars	Definition of Collaboration
Beder (1984)	The process of working with other organizations to achieve mutual benefits.
Hohmann (1985)	Collaboration is a response to the “increasing complexity of professionalism” through a combined effort to meet specific educational goal
Gray (1989)	A process through that parties who see different aspects of a

	problem can constructively explore their differences and search for solutions that go beyond their own limited vision of what is possible
Miller, Rossing and Steele (1990)	The parties share responsibilities and authority for basic decision making
Idol and West (1991)	Educational collaboration as a “structural process and interactive relationship”
Wood and Gray (1991)	Collaboration occurs when a group of autonomous stakeholders of a problem domain engage in an interactive process, using shared rules, norms and structures, to act or decide, on the issue related to that domain
Mattessich and Monsey (1992)	Mutually beneficial and well-defined relationship entered into by two or more organizations to achieve common goals. The relationship includes a commitment to a definition of mutual relationships and goals; a jointly developed structure and shared responsibility; mutual authority and accountability for success; and a sharing of resources and rewards
Abramson and Ronsenthal (1995)	Fluid process through which a group of diverse autonomous actors (organizations or individuals) undertakes a joint initiative, solve shared problems, or otherwise achieves common goals
O’Looney (1995)	Denote the processes and governance approaches
Cropper (1996)	IOC as a positive, purposive relationship between organizations that retain autonomy, integrity and distinctive identity and thus, the potential to withdraw from the relationship
Cropper (1996)	IOC as a positive, purposive relationship between organizations that retain autonomy, integrity and distinctive identity and thus, the potential to withdraw from the relationship
Bardach (1998)	Any joint activity by two or more agencies that is intended to increase public value by their working together rather than separately
Powell et al., (1999)	Organizational and inter-organizational structure where resources, power, and authority are shared and where people are brought together to achieve common goals that could not be accomplished by a single individual or organization independently
Austin (2000)	Collaboration as partnerships that involve equal partners working together toward satisfying mutually beneficial self-interests
Hord (1986); Kanter (1994); Legler and Reischl (2003)	Interorganizational collaboration as a developmental process has preceding conditions, a recognizable set of characteristics, and a dynamic process of planning and coordination; creating value in relationships and

	resources for the partners; transforming the organizations that participate in the collective activity; and perceive a mutuality of interests and benefits for the relationship.
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These definitions reflect earlier studies on IOC that focused on its antecedents, processes, and outcomes, as summarized by Wood and Gray (1991, as cited by Ada, 2013) and Gray and Wood (1991, as cited by Ada, 2013) in their review of IOC research. Ada (2013) presented a similar model or framework of IOC, which also credits the work of Thomas and Perry (2006):

Figure 1.

The antecedent-process-outcome framework of interorganizational collaboration. Adapted by Ada (2013) from Wood and Gray (1991), Gray and Wood (1991), and Thomson and Perry (2006).

Over the years, Gray's works and other studies on the social and relational characteristics of collaboration have grown and inspired further studies related to action learning, leadership, emotional dynamics, and discursive practices, among others (Schruijer, 2020). According to Koschmann (2022), these studies also provided a view of collaboration at the systems and economic levels. He further argued that, while communication is acknowledged in some of these studies as a relevant factor in collaboration, they treat communication as a variable rather than as an organizing force. An example of this is the work of Mattessich and Monsey in 1992 (as cited by Lundstrom, 2011) that extensively reviewed literature on factors that make collaboration successful. While they identified communication as one of the factors for successful collaboration that most researchers agree on, communication is still framed as a tool to gain trust and to manage information flow.

Despite collaboration being inherently communicative (Koschmann, 2022), research on the constitutive view of communication particular to the context of IOC has only started to gain interest in recent years. Antecedents to the paradigm shift toward a constitutive view of communication take its roots from the 1980s scholarship on interaction patterns and the 1990s to early 2000s scholarship on language/discourse (Putnam, 2022). However, studies using a CCO perspective have only been growing, at least, in the past two decades with the emergence of three major schools of CCO thinking in the early 2000s: Montreal School, Four-Flows School, and Luhmannian School (Putnam, 2022). Among the three, the Montreal School is most relevant to this study and discussed in more detail in Chapter 3. It provides the framework for analyzing conversation and text as communicative practices that constitute IOC through the process of co-orientation and the formation of authoritative text.

IOC as Communication

Following the emergence of CCO schools of thinking, interdisciplinary research on CCO continues to grow (Putnam, 2022). This includes CCO studies on interorganizational collaboration, which Putnam (2022) attributed to Arnaudi and Mills (2012), Koschmann (2013), Koschmann et al. (2012), and Koschmann (2022).

In his review of IOC literature, Koschmann (2022) organized the studies into 'broadly communicative' or have a general orientation toward CCO, and 'explicitly CCO' that specifically align with the CCO schools of thinking. While his review anchors collaboration in the context of civil society organizations, it remains relevant to the study given that the study looks into collaboration within the network of an international treaty organization. Koschmann (2022) also explained that bulk of CCO literature is based on the collaboration experience of civil society organizations.

Koschmann (2022) credits three (3) important works that started 'broadly communicative' collaboration scholarship. These include "Heath and Frey's (2004) *Communication Yearbook* chapter on community collaboration, Lewis's (2006) *Communication Yearbook* chapter on collaborative interaction, and Keyton, Ford, and Smith's (2008) article in *Communication Theory* that articulated a meso-level communicative model of collaboration." Together, these works contributed to placing communication as central to collaboration.

From these precursors, Koschmann (2022) also identified three (3) important bodies of research that continue to be relevant for broadly communicative collaboration studies. These include the works of Shumate's group on collaboration networks and communicative co-construction; Heath's dialogic approach; and Hardy, Grant, Lawrence, Maguire, and Phillips' organizational discourse.

Of particular interest to this study is Hardy, Lawrence, and Phillips' (1998) research on talk and action, where they presented a model explaining how conversations or talk lead to collective action. This model shows that talking or acts of communicating and the content of conversations among individuals create shared meaning that results in collective action.

Figure 2.

Model on talk and action (Hardy et al., 1998)

An important perspective from this model is the way it highlights identity, skills, and emotions as products of communication practices that enable action, specifically:

- Identity. This includes both individual and collective identities produced through conversations as well as through being excluded from such conversations. These identities affect how people behave in collaborative settings.
- Skills. This pertains to the abilities of individual members to act on a particular matter through culturally formed competencies. Skills enable

people to act on a problem, for example, because they are equipped with the tools to do so.

- Emotion. While conversations affect emotions either positively or negatively, the model highlights positive emotion as a motivation for action.

Hardy et al. (1998) summarizes the interaction between these three components by describing the process as “not merely additive, where a surplus of emotion can overcome a skill deficit. Rather, the components are inextricably tied to one another: for an ability to be enacted as a culturally valuable skill, it must be consistent with the participant’s identity and be motivated by appropriate emotions.”

On explicitly CCO collaboration literature, on the other hand, Koschmann (2022) considered research works that contributed to the CCO concepts of authority, agency, identity, and value. He added that inquiries in these studies were addressed using CCO concepts from the Montreal School, particularly on co-orientation. He noted that there are no studies on communicative constitution of collaboration using the Four-Flows and Luhmannian schools during the time of his review, but he recommended ways by which these schools may be used to study IOC. Koschmann (2022) also cited his works, some in collaboration with other authors, which include: a communicative model of value in collaborations and interorganizational relationships (Koschmann, Kuhn, and Pfarrer); collective identity (Koschmann); collaboration ineffectiveness (Koschmann); and the social construction of authority (Koschmann, Kopczynski, Opdyke, and Javernick-Will).

Communicative constitution view of IOC in an international context

Putnam (2022) attributes the international growth of CCO literature to the European Group for Organization Studies or EGOS' Standing Working Group on Organization as Communication and to international events that brought together CCO scholars worldwide. While there is evidence of CCO scholarship growing internationally, much is still to be done in organizing literature on the application of CCO in international contexts. Putnam (2022) notes that "CCO (and social science research more broadly) still has to pay better attention to research conducted, for instance, in Latin America, Africa or some parts of Asia."

As a starting point, CCO researchers may find it useful to thematically explore studies in collaboration at an international level. This includes the kind of activities or initiatives that countries or cultures usually collaborate on. For example, building the region's identity and culture as a community through the initiatives of the Association of Southeast Asian Nations or the ASEAN has been the focus of previous studies on Southeast Asian collaboration.

One of the sectors that ASEAN countries collaborate on is tourism. A study by Wong, Mistilis, and Dwyer (2011) proposed a model for ASEAN collaboration in tourism. The model explains intergovernmental collaboration on tourism as a phenomenon driven by eight (8) components: world economy and politics; regional economy and politics; actors and their interrelationships; preconditions of collaboration; arena of collaboration; the collaborative process; factors that facilitate the collaboration; and feedback mechanisms.

Figure 3.

A model for ASEAN collaboration in tourism (Wong et al, 2011)

The model further reflects the dynamism of ASEAN collaboration in tourism by highlighting the interactions among the identified components. Communication plays an important role, particularly in the third component, where relationships among state actors are formed. Wong et al. (2011) describe these interrelationships as a “sense of mutual understanding [that] allows them to work closer together”. They also identify such friendly relations as part of the *ASEAN Way* or the set of practices or characteristics that describe the ASEAN process of decision-making.

Another area of collaboration in Southeast Asia is in higher education. Partnerships in higher education have been moving from cooperation to collaboration and toward integrating the region and building an ASEAN community (Chao, 2022). In the case of consortia in higher education, collaboration is attractive for economic and efficiency reasons (Lang, 1975). Academic institutions can share resources and information through a consortium. Lang also adds that higher education consortia are incentivized by the prospect of accomplishing “collective activity improvements of

education and expansion of educational opportunity.” The need for concerted action in higher education is exacerbated by challenges that are “non-discriminatory, complex in nature and interrelated” (Kosaikanont, 2022). Kosaikanont added that regional partnerships in higher education necessitates the following:

- More equitable and distributed power among higher education institutions and other stakeholders involved in knowledge generation;
- More inclusive learning for all;
- More accessible and massified internationalization processes; and
- Transformed leadership for partnership.

While these examples do not necessarily situate communication as constitutive of collaboration, they present opportunities to understand collaboration in an international context that is specifically Southeast Asian. The lack of available literature reflects vast opportunities in providing communicative explanation of Southeast Asian collaboration, among other international contexts. As such, this study aims to contribute to the body of knowledge on CCO through a Southeast Asian perspective on IOC.

Chapter III

RESEARCH FRAMEWORK AND RESEARCH QUESTIONS

After highlighting the growing literature on communicative collaboration research in the previous chapter and the need for exploring an international or Southeast Asian context of IOC, this chapter explains how the accomplishment of IOC through communicative practices can be studied using a CCO approach. This chapter then culminates in the identification of the research problem and objectives.

Communicative Constitution of Organization

One of the popular approaches to CCO, and most relevant to this study, is the Montreal School developed by James Taylor, Francois Cooren, and their team in the Université de Montreal. This CCO approach is based on the notion that conversation and text are recursive, wherein “the output at each stage is typically applied to the input of succeeding stage” and this goes on repeatedly (Putnam, 2022). This constitutive view thus entails seeing “communication as a process that creates and reproduces collective meanings” (Koschmann and Isbell, 2009). These meanings are produced and reproduced through conversations and documents (Miranda, 2019).

Applying the Montreal School to the experience of organizations, van Vuuren and Knoers (2022) created a simplified model of the Montreal School’s concepts that explains how collective experience through conversation becomes authored into text. While van Vuuren and Knoers (2022) refer to this humorously as the ‘Montreal School for Dummies’ model, it adequately summarizes the processes involved in a laymanized manner.

Figure 4.

"Montreal School for Dummies" model (van Vuuren and Knoers, 2022)

This study is interested in understanding the nature and relationship of conversation and text toward accomplishing an action in the context of organizations. One of the key concepts from the Montreal School that could help explain how communication accomplishes interorganizational collaboration is co-orientation.

Co-orientation is a process wherein organizational members align their actions to common objectives through conversation and text (Taylor and Van Every, 2000 as cited in Koschmann, 2012). Groleau (2006 as cited in Fox and Jahn, 2022) differentiates co-orientation from other forms of interaction by stating that co-orientation is tied to an action or a goal. Co-orientation borrows from Newcomb's communication model using an A-B-X format, where A and B represent different individuals or groups and X represents the matter of concern (Fox and Jahn, 2022). Fox and Jahn explain further that A and B (or even more than two sets of individuals or groups) engage in conversation to address X. The meaning of X is produced and reproduced through conversation and recorded through text. Dawson (2022)

describes the role of text as “the recording of past cooriented conversations that now marks the result of collective action and upon which future conversations unfold.”

This brings us to another key concept that explains the conversation-text relationship, which is the authoritative text. Authoritative text, according to Kuhn (2008, as cited in Koschmann, 2012), is the culmination of the co-orientation process. Kuhn describes the authoritative text as “an abstract textual representation of the collective that portrays its structure and direction, shows how activities are coordinated and indicate relations of authority” and as “a network of meanings.” Such authority is demonstrated through the ability of text to coordinate and control activity (Kuhn, 2008 as cited in Dawson, 2022).

Koschmann also added that authoritative text shapes interorganizational collaboration in terms of defining roles and characterizing the collective organization. He further suggests that collective identity itself is an authoritative text in interorganizational collaboration that has the “ability to induce action and coordinate the activities of diverse stakeholders”.

This study explores the co-orientation among the collaborating parties of a consortium in order to describe how communicative practices form authoritative text. Text is given agency as evidenced by the collective action it results to. Authoritative texts also become a reference point that guides the decisions or actions of the collective group in its future undertakings.

Research Questions

The main purpose of this study is to understand how communication constitutes or accomplishes interorganizational collaboration of an international body. It moves beyond earlier studies on IOC that focused on its preconditions, processes, and

outcomes, as summarized by Gray and Wood (1991, as cited by Ada, 2013), in order to provide an explanation of IOC as a communication phenomenon. Specifically, this study looks into SEARCA's collaboration with higher education institutions on an international level through a consortium it initiated. The regular interaction of SEARCA with member institutions of the consortium over the years provides a richer context to draw from. As such, one of the objectives of this study is to identify the communicative practices of the international body and demonstrate how these practices are performed through conversation and text. The study will answer the research question:

What are the communicative practices that accomplish interorganizational collaboration in an international body?

Following the identification of communicative practices, the second objective of this study is to explain how such communicative practices constitute IOC. This completes our understanding of how communicative practices accomplish IOC. Such accomplishment is hinged on key concepts of the Communicative Constitution of Organization or CCO following the approach of the Montreal School. To reiterate, the second research question for the study is:

How do the communicative practices become constitutive of IOC?

Chapter IV

METHODOLOGY

Ethnomethodology

The study's interest in communicative practices as information that will help gain an understanding of interorganizational collaboration is more aligned with ethnomethodology. This research methodology has been developed by Harold Garfinkel, an American sociologist, as an approach to studying ordinary actions or commonsense knowledge (Davidson, 2012). It is interested in finding out how the actors or members of a social group make sense of or understand such everyday activities or commonplace information (Trace, 2016). In the context of organizations, the convergence between ethnomethodology and the communicative constitution of organizations (CCO) approach lies in the notion "that people at work share and follow routines that make it possible for them to understand their work" (Miranda, 2019).

Garfinkel explains this phenomenon through the concepts of accountability, indexicality, and reflexivity. In terms of sense-making, accountability is demonstrated such that members of a group are able to document or report the everyday activity being investigated (Maynard and Clayman, 2003). These documents are viewed as indexical or having a meaning that is tied to a context (Trace, 2016); and reflexive or displaying the ability of the members to explain or describe the social action being investigated (Garfinkel, 1967 as cited in Cole, 2005). This explanation also implies that communication is performative, wherein talk has an equivalent action (Cooren and Seidl, 2022).

Another alignment between CCO and ethnomethodology is their interest in the relationship between conversation and text. Have (as cited in Cole, 2005) highlighted

ethnomethodology's interest in natural documents as records that represent the social context of the phenomena being studied. Similarly, the recursive relationship between conversation and text is a key discussion point in CCO, particularly in the Montreal School. Cooren and Seidl (2022) demonstrated the influence of Garfinkel's work in the Montreal School by emphasizing that ethnomethodology "enjoins us to find *in interaction*, that is, *in communication*, the very root of social order (and therefore of organizational order)."

Following ethnomethodology, this study looks into conversation and text within the bounds of a consortium of Southeast Asian organizations. In particular, this study observed interactions that naturally occur in the consortium such as in meetings and workshops. It is concerned with understanding how communicative practices perform collaboration among the collective organization.

Study Site

To have a better understanding of the research environment, I will describe the setting of the study and my role in it as a researcher. This includes a discussion on the regional consortium for higher education, what it does, and how it is organized. I will then give focus on the Consortium Secretariat, composed of the Southeast Asian Regional Center for Graduate Study and Research in Agriculture (SEARCA) staff, as well as their roles and tasks.

The Consortium

SEARCA launched the Consortium in 1989 together with five higher education institutions (HEIs) representing five different countries from Southeast Asia as

founding members. The Consortium has since grown to include associate members and affiliate members, linking it to universities outside of the region.

The Consortium exists to “promote collaboration among its members to enhance graduate education and research in agriculture, environment, and natural resources for the benefit of the Southeast Asian region” and engages in the following activities at the time of this study:

- Support students and faculty members in their studies or research through grants
- Conduct annual activities for students, faculty, and executive board members
- Implement a graduate program developed by the consortium
- Participate in collaborative researches

The Consortium shares resources and exchanges information and expertise. This commitment is reflected in the form of membership in the Consortium. There are three categories of Consortium membership, particularly: regular, associate, and affiliate members. A regular member must be based within Southeast Asia with the capacity to provide academic and financial support to the Consortium. An associate member, on the other hand, has a similar capacity to provide academic and financial support to the Consortium but is located outside of Southeast Asia. Lastly, affiliate members may be based within or outside Southeast Asia and capable of supporting the Consortium in any form. Common to their qualifications is having established graduate education programs in agriculture and natural resources. All members are also expected to participate in the Consortium’s activities, contribute to the exchange

of resources, and financially support their participation in the Consortium or pay a corresponding membership fee, among others.

Organizational Chart

The member universities are represented in the Consortium by their high-level officials. They are organized such that each member university has two (2) representatives as members of the Executive Board and one (1) representative as coordinator. At the center of this structure is the Secretariat which manages the Consortium and provides support for the Executive Board members and the coordinators. Below is a visual representation of the Consortium's organizational chart:

Figure 5.

Organizational chart of the Consortium

The Executive Board is the Consortium's policymaking body that sets the direction for the Consortium, develops its policies and initiatives, approves the annual programs and budget, forges partnerships for collaboration, and raises funds, among others. Its members are composed of the highest-ranking officer of each institution designated as Chief Executive Officer, as well as officials who directly report to the Chief Executive Officers designated as Executive Officers.

On the other hand, Coordinators develop proposals for approval of the Executive Board, manage, monitor, and report ongoing programs and activities, and disseminate information about the Consortium. They also act as the focal person in their respective institutions responsible for implementing policies and decisions of the Executive Board, endorsing grant applications to the Consortium, and facilitating communication and coordination within their network.

As the central coordinating body, the Secretariat facilitates activities, manages funds, reviews endorsed grants, approves award letters to grant recipients, disburses funds according to the budget approved by the Executive Board, as well as other secretarial and administrative functions.

The operational processes of the Consortium are documented in a handbook. This contains the membership guidelines, organizational structure, management and coordination, profile of member HEIs, funding, and program components, among others.

The Consortium Secretariat

The Consortium Secretariat is composed of members of the SEARCA staff, headed by the Director. A unit in SEARCA is responsible for facilitating the activities of the Consortium as part of the Secretariat. During the time of this study, the unit has four members, which includes a Senior Program Head, two Program Specialists, and a Program Support Staff. The following shows the code names assigned to the members of the Secretariat, for their privacy, and their corresponding roles:

- Sec1 - Represents SEARCA as one of the Chief Executive Officers in the Consortium's Executive Board.

- Sec2 - Represents SEARCA as one of the Coordinators of the Consortium.
- Sec3 – Assists in the coordination of annual activities of the Consortium. Manages the content of the Consortium’s website, social media, and newsletter, among others.
- Sec4 – Assists in disbursing and monitoring the budget of the Consortium.
- Sec5 – Facilitates the processing of the grants awarded by the Consortium.

Communication in the Consortium

Given that the Consortium members are located in different countries, the Secretariat optimizes the use of electronic communication including, but not limited to, e-mail, instant messaging applications, and virtual meeting platforms. These are used mainly for announcements, inquiries, greetings, and coordinating various activities of the Consortium, among others. While Consortium members may communicate directly with other members, the Secretariat can also facilitate communication between or among members.

The Executive Board members of the Consortium meet once every year to formally discuss matters of concern. These may include planning the activities and budget for the succeeding year, assessing the performance of new members, evaluating applications for membership, and updates from each member institution, among others. *Sec1* usually moderates the meeting with the help of *Sec2*. A member institution is also assigned to host the Executive Board meeting in their home country and its Chief Executive Officer serves as co-moderator. While these formal meetings

happen only once a year, other meetings may be convened as needed. This is the case for the workshops that were observed in this study.

Data Collection

In order to give context to the communicative practices of the Consortium, documents like memos, guidelines or process manuals, reports, and minutes of the meetings, among others, were initially considered in data collection. Interviews were also conducted for purposes of clarification. Where applicable, I observed meetings of the group to be studied in order to capture information from the group's natural setting. It will also help me gain a better understanding of group dynamics and relevant contexts.

This study relies heavily on the availability of documents and records. As such, the study had to be open for adjustments in the course of data collection and analysis. I also took the necessary steps in complying with the requirements from SEARCA as Consortium Secretariat, including permissions to conduct this study.

Primary data collected include available audio or video recordings of meetings. I selected meetings that are intended for decision-making and/or collaborating for a specific project or activity, such as workshops, Executive Board meetings, and coordination meetings, among others. During the time of this study, most of the meetings were conducted through virtual platforms due to the limitations caused by the COVID-19 pandemic. This means most of the video and audio recordings were generated from these virtual platforms.

The main data used in the analysis came from two Consortium workshops conducted in 2022. These workshops were a result of a decision made during a meeting among its Executive Board in the previous year to participate in a call for

project proposals to be funded through a program of the European Union (EU). It was also decided in that Executive Board meeting that the project will be in relation to a previous Consortium-initiated project that was successfully awarded an EU grant, which is a graduate program on food security and climate change. A Consortium member was also identified as the project lead. These initial agreements serve as pre-conditions to interorganizational collaboration or collaboration among the Consortium members during and after the workshops.

As the Consortium Secretariat, SEARCA organized the workshops that aimed to provide an overview of the funding institution's requirements and expected deliverables, assign Consortium members to facilitate different work packages of the proposal and review the outputs for each work package, among others. Each workshop is around three hours long and was conducted almost two weeks apart. SEARCA representatives provided the Consortium with background information on the proposed project as well as the parameters set by the funding institution. They also facilitated the discussions among Consortium members.

On the other hand, Consortium members were given the opportunity to ask questions and express their opinions about the proposed project. Since expectations were discussed at the start of the first workshop, the Consortium members were made aware that there will be tasks or work packages to be assigned to each of them. In the first workshop, Consortium members finalized the proposal topic, appointed the project lead, and agreed on the division and assignment of work packages. The second workshop served as an opportunity for the Consortium members to regroup and present the outputs they were able to come up with after almost two weeks of asynchronous work. Clarifications were made toward finalizing the detailed work packages. A shared folder was then created to allow SEARCA and the other members

to see the different work packages under the proposal. It was then up to the project lead, with the help of SEARCA, to package the proposal and submit it for consideration by the funding institution.

The next step includes transcribing the video and audio recordings to be used for analysis. As a beginner with no prior experience in transcribing data for qualitative research, I opted to start with transcribing the meeting recordings orthographically or verbatim. Transcribing the data myself, while time-consuming, is also necessary to maintain the confidentiality of the recordings. Names of participants, institutions, and other sensitive information were redacted to further maintain confidentiality. For example, members of the Secretariat were labeled as *Sec* followed by a corresponding number (e.g. *Sec1*), while participants were labeled *CM* for Consortium member followed by a number that corresponds to an institution and a letter that corresponds to the participant (e.g. *CM4A*).

Initial observations from these transcripts have been noted with the intention of using these as a guide for identifying emerging patterns of communicative practices. Main questions for reflection include, “What communication behaviors can be observed from the group in facilitating collaboration with another organization?”, “What are the roles of the individual members in interorganizational collaboration and what communicative practices reflect these roles?”, and “What texts are referred to in conversations?”, among others.

Data Analysis

The transcripts from each workshop were divided into conversation segments. Performativity, or the concept that equates utterance with action, is used in analyzing the conversation segments. The concept of performative utterance was introduced by

John Austin in 1962 in his book, *How to do things with words*, wherein he described performativity as 'to say something is to do something' (Gond and Cabantous, 2015). In CCO studies, performativity is interpreted at the level of conversation and textualization processes (Gond et al, 2015). This means that communicative practices contribute to the creation and recreation of an organization through conversation and text that perform the organization into being.

Initially, I started looking into the conversation segments for words that perform action by simply being uttered (e.g. share, note, hear, agree, etc.) or words that give context to an action (e.g. very good = praise). I, then, labeled these conversation segments according to the action it results or contributes to.

This process generated 12 codes that correspond to communicative practices. These were reviewed for consistency of meaning or applicability throughout the transcripts. Each of these codes were then collapsed further into three broader categories or meta-themes that demonstrate coordination of action among members of the interorganizational network or shape the collaboration activity. This is explained in more detail in the next chapter.

Chapter V

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This study aims to understand the accomplishment of IOC through the communicative practices of an international body. Toward this end, the study should be able to demonstrate how conversation and text perform communicative practices as well as explain how these communicative practices become constitutive.

Twelve communicative practices were identified from the data and were further organized according to three broader categories or meta-themes, particularly: contextualizing, consensus building, and confirming commitment. This chapter presents how these three main communicative practices constitute IOC in the context of an international body.

Communicative Practices

The presentation of results begins with addressing the first research question, which is: *What are the communicative practices on interorganizational collaboration of an international body?* In the previous chapter, it was discussed that the concept of performativity was used in determining how conversation and text correspond to communicative practices. This was applied through identifying key words or context cues in the transcript that result to action by being uttered or demonstrated. The next tables show the process of analyzing conversation segments into communicative practices that perform IOC.

Providing background information. Giving detailed information helps participants better understand the context of a project, activity, or task. Information shared by the Secretariat is usually lengthy and thorough, which

shows that contextualizing is meant to give a complete picture of the collaboration. By doing so, participants have the same information or input to work with, regardless of their level of familiarity with previous collaboration activities within the Consortium.

Table 2.

Providing background information

Workshop & Line Numbers	Conversation Segment	Key Word/s
W1, 18-23	Sec1: Thank you, doctor Sec2. Let me just share my screen again (proceeds to share the screen). Ok, so we start first with the review of the discussions made during the [meeting] related to this new proposal we will be needing for the [EU] funding. So, during the [meeting] on December 16 to 17, 2021, the consortium secretariat presented the proposal for possible submission to the [EU program] actions, particularly for (inaudible) on partnerships for transformation on higher education...	share, presented
W1, 667-770	Sec3: (Pre-recorded video) ...Now, we have to understand the difference between sub-contractor and a contractor for goods and purchases...goods and services that we have purchased. So, sub-contracts concern the implementation of actual tasks, which may be crucial to the project, but which have been outsourced and this needs to be written in the proposal right from the start that we are outsourcing a particular task. Otherwise, if we do not write it in our proposal, then we cannot claim a subcontracting cost for that specific task later on. On the other hand, contracts of goods or services are those that are necessary for a beneficiary to implement its work. So, it can be a purchase of a big equipment or just some petty goods. And the price for these contracts will be declared under the budget of the beneficiary for which the purchase was made, not to the sub-contract. So, examples of sub-contracts are those for event organizers whom we contracted to organize a conference. Just as I mentioned, part of the tasks described in our proposal. So, this is something that is purely third party. The beneficiaries do not participate in the organization of the conference. On the other hand, example of contracts for purchases are, say, contracts for audit certificates of our financial statements, or	understand, mentioned, see

	contracts for translation of documents, publication of brochures, creation of websites, or for venues or catering for a meeting if the organization of that meeting is not with sub-contracted, or for hiring IT or consultants needed for the project. I hope you see the difference.	
W1, 997-1035	Sec2: (Pre-recorded audio)...Before we identify the work packages, let me first discuss the budget because we need to include these in the details of the work packages.	discuss
W2, 38-68	Sec1: Thank you, doctor Sec2. So, moving to our next item in the agenda, I will be presenting a review of the previous meeting regarding our plan proposal. So, let me share my screen. This was previously sent also via e-mail. So, last January 18, we held our first consortium meeting to discuss the proposal to be submitted to the [EU program]. So, among the target EU priorities we chose Green Deal and Digital Transformation and Data Technologies...	presenting, share
W2, 69-98	Sec3: Ok. Thank you very much. So, we have Partner4 joining us in the project for the second HEI from Malaysia. For partner beneficiaries in the EU, we wrote to CM13, specifically to doctor CM13A, who was also our contact during the [MS program]. She expressed interest from CM13 to be part of our project anew. In fact, she had several suggestions. She said that she is...that CM13 is part of another EU-funded project called (project1) and this is made up of nine EU universities. And they are also...part of the project is also to come up with micro credentials. So, she said that she is suggesting a knowledge exchange event on the establishment of a micro credential system, whereby these EU universities could share their experience on the matter. She is also keen on CM13 participating in the development of an online course, especially one related to forestry sector. They're also doing one right now in another project also with Indonesian partners. And she said they also want to explore the development of digital measures to facilitate international student mobilities. Though, these are going to be virtual mobilities. So, these are the suggestions that she made and she has already brought to the central administration of CM13 this proposal. In fact, she is asking for more details, but I promised to give her that after this workshop. And, uh, for PARTNER1, we contacted doctor PARTNER1A. He was very active in the [MS program]. He would also be happy for PARTNER1 to be part of the project, except that he wants to see the details of the work packages and would probably, uh, want to	wrote, said, promised, contacted, informed

	<p>have a short meeting to discuss how PARTNER1 can make a meaningful contribution to the project. So, I told him again that after this meeting we will come back to him for more details. But I also informed him about the suggestions made by CM13, so he could also think of similar contributions from the side of PARTNER1. Unfortunately, doctor PARTNER1A has not yet responded to my e-mail, but I'll send him a WhatsApp message later. So, I have not...well, I have not yet contacted Partner2 because I wanted to see as an affiliate partner the contribution also that they could make after our work package details have been presented. So, on my part, that's it and, uh...Sorry. Now, sec1, perhaps we can go to the next item.</p>	
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Giving instructions. Instructions guide the participants on how a task should be done according to a set of requirements. In the case of the workshops, the Secretariat needed to emphasize every now and then the requirements of the funder for the proposal. Giving instructions is also done as a way of putting order in the workshop itself. Sec3 illustrated this by requesting presenters to upload their presentations in a shared web-based folder for reference of all the participants. The intention is to collect and organize all the information presented, as well as to give participants the opportunity for review and feedback.

Table 3.

Giving instructions

Workshop & Line Numbers	Conversation Segment	Key Word/s
W1, 667-770	<p>Sec3: (Pre-recorded video) Now we come to the selection of partners. Note that in our proposal, we have to indicate the list of our partners and the roles that each play in the project, which may be either as coordinator, beneficiary, affiliated entity, associated partner, in-kind contributor, or sub-contractor. Hence, we must know the difference between each of these. The coordinator is the project lead. So, it is the beneficiary, which is the central contact point for the EU, and represents</p>	note, [have to] indicate

	<p>the consortium towards EU. The other beneficiaries are those that participate in the grant agreement. Note that in the previous project, [MS program], CM4 as coordinator signed the grant agreement with the EU and, in turn, CM4 signed partnership agreements with each of the other beneficiaries. And so, that's how the other beneficiaries get to sign the grant agreement.</p>	
<p>W1, 997-1035</p>	<p>Sec2: (Pre-recorded audio) Finally, we have the identification of work packages. Note that all project activities should be grouped in logical, consistent, and structured way into separate work packages. Each work package must present a clear, logical link to the project objectives and to the other work packages. They should constitute a sub-part of the project and leads to the achievement of the overall goals. There should be a minimum of two work packages. One for the management and coordination of the project activities and another to produce the outputs related to the project goals. However, we can have as many as we need but we are cautioned not to have too many of them, and try to limit to five or six. Work package one is usually on project management and coordination. But we may also include any other activity that does not relate to any of the other work packages and leads to a specific result directly linked to the project as a whole. For the other work packages, we have to indicate the objectives, the activities to be implemented, and outputs. For the outputs, we distinguish between milestones and deliverables. Milestones are the control points that help to chart progress, such as kick-off meetings, the steering committees, the first draft of a survey, or a prototype, while deliverables are outputs that we commit to submit to EU and may be in the form of publication, leaflets, progress reports, brochures, or lists. We need to be as specific as possible. For example, we should indicate the number of events; and for each event the title, the content, the duration, the number of participants, and where the participants are coming from, for example. If it's a publication the number of pages, the language it is written or languages more than one, the format if printed or electronic, and the number of printed copies if any for each language if more than one. Because the project duration is limited to only three years, we need to be realistic about what we can achieve. The scope of the project should be large enough to make an impact, but we do not need to produce an excessive number of outputs. And in the proposal, we only need to indicate the major outputs. We don't need to include minor items such as internal</p>	<p>include, [have to] indicate</p>

	<p>working papers, minutes of meetings. However, it is assumed that each meeting and each event is properly documented and evaluated by the attendees. Now, overall, we need to limit the number of our deliverables to ten or fifteen. And in fact, we may be asked to reduce the number further once our proposal is awarded and during the discussion in the grant preparation. For each deliverable, we also need to specify when we will upload it to the portal.</p>	
W2, 755-788	<p>Sec3: ...so we can do this face to face. Uh, I note that when we gave you the template, there is just one matrix, <i>no</i>, for the budget. But you can do that on a per activity basis. So, you have a field for each activity, how much you need. And then, just do the...the totals later into one, uh, table.</p> <p>CM7A: Ok. Thank you.</p> <p>Sec3: That's how we did it, uh, in the [MS program]. So, we have one worksheet for each of the activities, then just add it later.</p>	note, add
W2, 1012-1015	<p>Sec3: Ok. Before I forget, we will ask all those who presented to please upload your presentations in the shared folder corresponding to your work packages, so we can take a look at it. Everyone can take a look at it later and perhaps there might be other comments that we have missed, so we can share those comments to the presenters. Thank you.</p>	ask, upload, look
W2, 1343-1380	<p>Sec3: But CM4 will be like encoding all of these and uploading in the EU platform.</p> <p>CM4A: Ok.</p> <p>Sec3: Yes. For all of the five regular members who were there in the last project, as well as CM8, they all have PICs already. But, uh, I think CM9 has a PIC because they are involved in a number of other EU-funded projects. Uh, we can always check this in the registry. Sec1, could you check if CM12 and CM6 as well as Partner4 also have PICs already validated?</p> <p>Sec1: Ok po. We'll check.</p>	encoding, uploading, check
W2, 1397-1446	<p>Sec3: ...So, those are just suggestions (pause) and I believe now we are into...because it is 11:47, next steps or moving forward. What do we do now? So, first is that you should upload all the presentations in the shared folder. So, we can already take a look at them and plug in our proposed edits and other comments. And then, we need to set a date. I do not know if you wish to have another meeting or we can just set a date for</p>	upload, take [a look], plug in

	<p>you to come up with a revised budget...revised work package proposal. Because, for example, for work package three...two, we're going to delete some of the activities because they will already be done by work package three or work package four. Plus, you're going to have more details in your budget proposals. So, we'd like to see them...hmmm, February 7...Today is January 31, so a week from now is February...February what? February 7 (pause) so that, if we have comments from what we will see on February 7, we will come back to you, like on February 10 and tell you that, uh, we cannot accommodate this or please put this into your budget because we think you missed this. So...we can have another...we can have some more time for the final, final revisions. February 7? Ok. Doctor CM2B says yes. So, by February 7, sec1 will pester you if we don't see your uploaded, revised work package proposals by the end of the day.</p>	
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Aligning. Similar to giving instructions, aligning also puts order in the workshop itself by ensuring that discussions remain within the bounds of the collaborative work. Participants follow an agreed-upon order or agenda of discussion prepared by the Secretariat, which is maintained through signaling when a new topic or agenda item may be discussed. Participants would often ask permission from the facilitating Secretariat member whether a topic can be opened for discussion or continue to be discussed. The Secretariat also demonstrated this by expressing their expectations from the participants (e.g. each regular member of the Consortium should lead a work package), highlighting decisions to be made, and reminding participants on the order of the agenda.

Table 4.

Aligning

Workshop & Line Numbers	Conversation Segment	Key Word/s
W1, 26-54	Sec2: Can we go first to the agenda? Sorry. Before I called you for the agenda presentation, I	expect, emphasize, envision

	<p>think we have to go first to the...so that everyone will know what to expect. Again, members of the consortium and the participants representing the different members of the consortium, these will be our...these are what we expect for this meeting. But before that I just want to emphasize the objective of this workshop really is we expect to come up with the project objectives, intended partners, main objectives, activities and expected outputs leading to the identification of the work packages and its assigned lead institutions. That is very crucial. Second, we shall set the date for the next meeting, our meetings where we expect the assigned lead institution to present their proposals for their specific work packages. So, don't worry. We'll be presenting all this work possible...we'll be discussing these different work packages including its activities, milestones, deliverables, and budget. So, that's the next meeting. We want really...we envision the six regular members of the consortium, ideally six regular members, to lead a particular work package. And of course, the agenda as we will be reviewing is to review and discuss the discussion made during the consortium Executive Board meeting, which sec1 will be presenting later related to the new proposal for [EU] funding. Second is the final proposal topic and we finalize the project coordinator and the lead, then go to the proposal development. We will be presenting several slides on this one. Presentation by doctor Sec3 on particularly who will be our partners from countries to higher education institutions outside and within EU, non-higher education institution partners, like academic consortium or industry partners and other government...work packages, which is very crucial because we will be identifying work packages here and we develop the milestones and deliverables, division of responsibilities and resources, time schedule, project management structure, dissemination and communication activities. And we have budget, which is really important. We will be introduced to different...how to develop the budget and we have to schedule now for the next workshop where work package leaders, that's the institutions, will be presenting their proposal.</p>	
W1, 144-185	<p>Sec2: Ok. Thank you, sec3, for that explanation and I hope we could also follow it up from our institutions. And actually that [MS program] is a pilot and now we are moving towards this micro credit kind of education. And I think the pandemic has really made some...we have limited progress on this one. Ok. Thank you. Any other comment before we proceed to the second agenda?</p>	proceed

W1, 224-246	Sec2: ...As we move forward, we need to finalize now. May I call first, who will be represented by CM4?	need [to finalize]
W1, 311-329	Sec2: Thank you very much for that update. Yeah. We could see really great support from CM4 as they will be leading the...this project. And of course, from other consortium members which will be...as we go further, you could see now how each of us have a lot of rooms to enter for this working packages that we have to lead as we go along. Ok. Let's proceed now to the second presentation on proposal development.	proceed
W1, 490-506	Sec3: Thank you. There are five core courses in our [MS program]. The changing climate and its impacts on natural resources, agriculture, and food security; food security and food systems in a dynamic environment; impact assessment and evaluation of projects and policies; sustainability assessment in agricultural production and food processing, that's actually the summer school; and research methods. And these were, uh, designed by teams with members coming from each of our consortium. We are not...I mean, if these are not appropriate for this project then we leave it to the team. But for each of these, we already have the course analysis and we can just...I don't know, pick topics perhaps. Say for changing climate and its impact on natural resources, agriculture, and food security, part of the course includes discussion on earth and climate systems, the signs of climate change, anthropogenic drivers, climate change projections and scenarios, impacts on natural resources on agriculture, on food security, and then adaptation strategies, mitigation strategies, and so on. Uh, so for each of these courses, we have all of these topics. And that's why we are saying we can just pick topics out of these and perhaps make modules out of it, but...uh, as I said this is for the consortium to decide. So, for all of these, food security and food system, the pillars, the food production, uh, systems and security, processing, food quality and safety, food nutrition and security, socio economic impacts, food security initiatives assessment, and so on. We have a handbook for all of these[MS program] courses and, uhm, perhaps we will share...uh, a link to you so you can go through them.	pick, decide
W1, 569-591	CM1B: I think...uh...uhm...in terms of policies, although in this specific objective I'm quite...uh, I mean in terms of the word revised, it might be too stringent on that because currently for UPLB, for example, I think we can exploit, sorry for the word, exploit some of the policies. Let's say the	noted/noting

	<p>equivalency. Let's say if you have gathered three short courses, then we can somehow bulk that and that can be equivalent to one course. So we can do that, I think, in UPLB to somehow exploit that policy. So I think for revised, we can make it more general like develop a system or craft university policies that can be adopted or can be modified to fit the specific university rules...something like that.</p> <p>Sec2: Yeah. That's noted. We will be noting it. We will not finalize it. Any other comments? (Reading from the screen) Revise university policies influence...leverage...develop micro credentials modules...All your comments in the chat box will be noted. Any other comment regarding the third objective? Revise university policies to enable enrolments. Revise university policies to make...to make micro credit-ready universities...something like that...or micro credit-friendly universities...uhm, yeah. Any other comments on that one to make it more not like we are banging on the universities but we are working with them to make it really...I think CM1D has a very great mind in revising this one.</p>	
W1, 651-666	<p>Sec2: ...We have no more specific objectives there? (long pause) Ok. Now, let's...I think we are ok. Now, let's proceed now to agenda number two...oh, agenda number two, part of agenda number two on selection of partners. Uh, sec3 will be presenting on what do you mean by partners, all the specific names of the partners based on the [EU] template.</p>	proceed
W1, 667-770	<p>Sec3: (Pre-recorded video)...Also, CM4 opted to sign one partnership agreement between CM4 and other beneficiaries. However, because we need to submit the partnership agreement to the EU up to a given point, CM4 felt that it would be best to sign partnership agreements bilaterally because there are some institutions which may need to have the partnership agreements reviewed by their legal departments before signing and could take some time. And so, when the time came to submit the partnership agreements, we were able to submit most of them last time and the other that came in late, we just submitted afterwards. And that was fine because we have submitted most of them during the deadline. The affiliated entities are just like beneficiaries. They may be funded for their engagement in the project. They should also fulfill the same conditions for participation and funding. And they also need to be registered in the EU participant registry and have a valid participant identification code or PIC. The only difference now, the affiliated entities, which is a term new for</p>	need

	<p>this call, is that they do not need to sign the grant agreement. And an example given by the program guide for affiliated entities are international organizations. So, I placed there for example, SEARCA.</p>	
W1, 778-781	<p>Sec3: Alright. So, for the region, as have been mentioned, because of the composition of the consortium, definitely, we have partner beneficiaries from Indonesia, Malaysia, Philippines, and Thailand. But we need a minimum of two HEIs from each partner country. With Indonesia, we already have three. Do we need any more partner HEIs from Indonesia?</p>	need
W1, 997-1035	<p>Sec2: (Pre-recorded audio) Finally, we have the identification of work packages. Note that all project activities should be grouped in logical, consistent, and structured way into separate work packages. Each work package must present a clear, logical link to the project objectives and to the other work packages. They should constitute a sub-part of the project and leads to the achievement of the overall goals. There should be a minimum of two work packages. One for the management and coordination of the project activities and another to produce the outputs related to the project goals. However, we can have as many as we need but we are cautioned not to have too many of them, and try to limit to five or six. Work package one is usually on project management and coordination. But we may also include any other activity that does not relate to any of the other work packages and leads to a specific result directly linked to the project as a whole. For the other work packages, we have to indicate the objectives, the activities to be implemented, and outputs. For the outputs, we distinguish between milestones and deliverables. Milestones are the control points that help to chart progress, such as kick-off meetings, the steering committees, the first draft of a survey, or a prototype, while deliverables are outputs that we commit to submit to EU and may be in the form of publication, leaflets, progress reports, brochures, or lists. We need to be as specific as possible. For example, we should indicate the number of events; and for each event the title, the content, the duration, the number of participants, and where the participants are coming from, for example. If it's a publication the number of pages, the language it is written or languages more than one, the format if printed or electronic, and the number of printed copies if any for each language if more than one. Because the project duration is limited to only three years, we need to be realistic about what we can achieve. The scope of the project</p>	note, need

	<p>should be large enough to make an impact, but we do not need to produce an excessive number of outputs. And in the proposal, we only need to indicate the major outputs. We don't need to include minor items such as internal working papers, minutes of meetings. However, it is assumed that each meeting and each event is properly documented and evaluated by the attendees. Now, overall, we need to limit the number of our deliverables to ten or fifteen. And in fact, we may be asked to reduce the number further once our proposal is awarded and during the discussion in the grant preparation. For each deliverable, we also need to specify when we will upload it to the portal. Before we identify the work packages, let me first discuss the budget because we need to include these in the details of the work packages.</p>	
W1, 1302-1312	<p>Sec2: University reforms and quality plan. That's a huge...can we specify these university reforms? Flexible...university reforms, that's a huge task. So, we have to reduce it to a more...university reforms for flexible course...Anyway, just put it in closed parentheses. This is more on the flexible learning...flexible micro...micro credit reforms towards...quality plan towards micro credit, uh, modality (pause). Then, next is communication and dissemination. This is more on the promotion, packaging, branding. Then, monitoring...I think that's ok for now. Then, maybe sec3 let's proceed to who will be the leading? Who will lead in this different project?</p>	proceed, put
W1, 1378-1425	<p>Sec3: That's correct. That's why when I made the presentation earlier, after the proposed work package title, I described what I expected out of that work package. Uh, yes, it might also be that in the development of the modules you already take care in the development and delivery of the micro credential courses, you may already take care of the monitoring and evaluation. But as mam CM1C mentioned, it may be nice to have a separate work package for this. Remember they also mentioned last time about external assessment, a third party assessment, and so on. So, this may be viewed in that way, but, uh...</p>	remember
W1, 1515-1520	<p>Sec2: Yeah. So, we expect before January 31 different packages...work packages teams should be meeting and discuss and write it up and we will be following it up on SEARCA side. (pause) OK? So, 31 is ok? Yeah, it's ok. Everyone is nodding their head, sec3. So, 31 January, what time? Same time?</p> <p>Sec3: Time? 9AM.</p>	expect, nodding

	<p>Sec2: 9 to 12.</p> <p>Sec3: Yes.</p> <p>Sec2: So, this is very critical and we'll have some presentation and input from the different groups.</p> <p>Sec3: Ok.</p>	
W1, 1526-1537	<p>Sec2: Schedule of next workshop for work packages, leaders will be presenting their proposals. Ok. Thank you very much, sec3 and the team, for your active participation. I know everyone is very passionate and they are really very itchy to start the writing and the...of the different work packages and we have now leaders to do this and, uh, I hope we could come up as we reach August...uh, August, January 31, we already ready and we will...SEARCA, we'll be knocking at your door to make this happen. Ok. Any other final comments? SEARCA will be the...we will be communicating to you to give you the summary of this meeting and we expect your team as well as the assigned team leaders, universities, then you form your own team to make this happen. Uhm, so January 31, that's it. That will be our crucial next meeting workshop. Anything, sec3?</p>	hope, expect
W2, 69-98	<p>Sec3: Yes. Good morning to everyone. Let me just share my screen and this...this...Uh, ok. So, this is an update on our partner beneficiaries both from the EU and in Asia. So, last meeting as Sec1 mentioned...Why is this not moving? Ok. We have decided on the partner beneficiaries in Asia and we thank CM8, CM9, and CM12 for confirming their participation in our project. For Malaysia, we heard from CM2 that they are targeting Partner4, but we would like to get the confirmation right now, dean CM2A?</p>	share, update, mentioned, decided, heard
W2, 202-226	<p>Sec3: ...Although, as you mentioned, the budget still has to be finalized. Uhm, for some comments, of course in each of the activities mentioned, we noted that you have included all the five...no, the six consortium regular members and SEARCA. But perhaps we will need to include also our other partners, especially for example, in the kick-off, I would like to believe that you want to have all of them, no, including Partner4, and CM13, and Partner1, if they are joining us and, of course, CM8 and CM12. Uh, you answered my second question and that is on whether the meetings will be face-to-face or online. You already mentioned that some of them would probably be online. I do not know if you are planning for some face-to-face</p>	noted, mentioned

	<p>meetings. We just want to know because they will have an implication in the budget because travel from one country to another would involve budget, plus the accommodation and the (pause) others related to the stay. Uh, I also find it nice that you will come up with guidelines on the financial allocation...</p>	
<p>W2, 498-549</p>	<p>Sec3: Ok. As long as we're just limited to five, no, five courses for development. Ok. Mmhmm, and then you asked whether coming up with the centralized LMS or linking this to the different universities using their own LMS. Again, we probably have to discuss that later. I...</p> <p>CMC1: Yes. So, that's our dilemma in our team because we said, are we going to...are we going to come up with a separate learning management system or are we going to come up with one? So, we don't know if, uh, we are going to use our own...our own learning platform? Or will the consortium...consortium members would decide to use their own, but we'll just have to guide them on maybe the look and the features that would go into it? So, we have to agree on that.</p> <p>Sec3: Yeah. We probably have to know the status...or what are the different members using, because I know CM1, for example, has a...I don't know...</p> <p>CM1C: Moodle. We have Moodle. We have Canvas.</p> <p>CM1D: And Canvas.</p> <p>Sec3: Ok. Ok. So, these are the questions...</p> <p>CM1C: So, we don't know if, uh, the other consortium members would have the same learning management system because we need to at least have the same...the same, you know, the same features, the same look in terms of...even if we have different platforms, at least the content would look the same so that when we do the transfer of credits, there will be less contentions, less doubts on how did you get this course from CM1 or how did you get this course from CM5? Oh, we have the same. So, that means, there's not that much problem in terms of transferring a credit.</p> <p>Sec3: Yeah. So, in that case, it would probably be nice to have like a centralized LMS for this, but may we ask the other consortium members on what are you using in your respective universities? Uh, dean CM2A, at CM2, do you have a</p>	<p>limited, agree, consider</p>

	<p>centralized LMS for the...for the whole university? (long pause) Dean CM2A? (long pause) Doctor CM4A for CM4? Or anybody from CM4? (long pause) Yes?</p> <p>CM4B: Yes. For CM4, we have university central LMS and we use Moodle, but...but that is only for university register student. So, I agree that we should have a central system. Otherwise, uh, our students might be confused because when taking a different subject during a different program.</p> <p>CM1C: Yeah.</p> <p>CM4B: Even...even CM4, we use Moodle but we have our own interface. So, maybe a different university also has their own and it might be difficult for students.</p> <p>CM1D: Mam sec3? Doctor sec3?</p> <p>Sec3: Yes, CM1D, mam.</p> <p>CM1D: Yeah, because, uhm currently CM1 is to undergo...undertake a CHED project and we are looking at access elements as a common learning management system for a consortium of universities. From what we have gathered from the estimate, I think, uhm, using access elements, which is a Moodle based application, would cost about [amount in euros] for four hundred users. So, if we are looking at...but I think that is for two or three years of use. But because if we're going to be doing something that is across universities, it might be better to consider something like that so that when we collaborate, we're collaborating on only one platform. And if most universities here are using Moodle based systems, then it should not be a difficult transition, I guess, but then it's separate from the university's system so that it doesn't cause confusion between the collaborative programs and the, uhm, in-house programs of each of the universities. However, that has to be incorporated into the budget...just bringing it up because of the budget concerns on that. Thank you.</p> <p>Sec3: That's right. I believe that is also what our colleague from CM4 is suggesting that we should have like a centralized LMS so that if students will take a micro credential at CM1 and CM4, for example, there will not be much difference. Alright. If it's [amount in euros], mam CM1D, for four hundred users for three years, then yeah, I think</p>	
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	<p>that's good enough. We just have to put that in our proposed budget.</p> <p>CM1D: We can also ask, mam, so that we're sure also and if we're considering a larger number of users, it might be more cost efficient to get a package that is larger. Ok. We'll ask. We'll ask po. Thank you.</p> <p>Sec3: Thank you. And then, we'll ask CM1 to put that into their budget, uh, because the LMS will be part of work package two. So, yes...</p> <p>CM1D: Yes, mam.</p>	
<p>W2, 560-600</p>	<p>CM9B: Ok. Good morning, everyone. I'm from CM9. My concern, mam, is currently, for instance, we are offering joint courses with [university]. And then, our problem, they took three courses with us cause he was taking an MS in [university]. But when I saw his diploma, because he applied for PhD scholarship here, our university was never mentioned. So, there was a joint offering. Supposedly, it's covered by the MOU, and then when I saw his diploma, there was never mentioned of CM9 as one of the, let's say, facilitator of the course. So, that is my concern now because there are also other universities offering us to collaborate with them. So, first, my question is, with this micro credentials, what program are we offering? If we offer it here in the Philippines, for instance, they have masters in sustainable development in Belgium. So, is this the same...is this related to a specific program because if it's related to a specific graduate program, if we offer it here in the Philippines, we have to submit this to CHED for COPC approval of the graduate program. But if we just offer to specific courses, to what graduate program are we going to offer it? And then, secondly, will the diploma of the students, after they finish taking courses with us, would include CM9 as one of the offering institutions? So, these are some concerns that we have to tackle because there are many now that they are offering collaborative courses with different universities and that is my problem, no. So, how this would...how we can solve about it if we have a system now with SEARCA, <i>no</i>, in trying to facilitate this joint offering of different courses with the other consortium members. And then, third, with regards to the course manual, we have here at CM9 the CM9 e-learning environment wherein we can incorporate it in our environment. We offer some specific courses. So, that is some of my major concerns.</p>	<p>decided, exploring, agreed</p>

	<p>Sec3: Thank you, mam CM9B. Uh, in the first meeting, we have decided that this micro credential courses can be stand-alone courses.</p> <p>CM9B: Ok.</p> <p>Sec3: It can be taken by anyone who is interested in the course simply for lifelong learning...</p> <p>CM9B: Ah, ok.</p>	
W2, 615-645	<p>CM1D: Uhm, do we go by, mam, UNDP rate for subsistence allowances and accommodations?</p> <p>Sec3: Ah, I don't know because in the previous project, it is all unit cost. The EU has a particular unit cost, but now...</p> <p>CM1D: Ok.</p> <p>Sec3: ...we are free, no, as long as we can justify, they said, as long as we can justify the cost. I don't...actually, I do not know how much is the UN rate.</p> <p>CM1D: Mam, the UNDP rate changes from month to month depending also on the country and the location in the country. So, that's why it might be important also to have...I'm just thinking in terms of tentative venues also for these meetings so that we know how to budget it. Ok, mam. That's noted. Thank you very much.</p> <p>Sec3: Oh, in the activity...</p> <p>CM1C: We can go to Thailand.</p> <p>Sec3: Yeah. We also note that in the activity.</p>	note
W2, 713-736	<p>Sec3: Thank you very much, doctor CM7C. Uh, yes, that was also good. But just a clarification, first, on the duration of the project. So, we note that, uh, the deadline of submission of our proposal to [EU] is February 17 of 2022. But the awarding, usually by August...late August, we should know whether our proposal has been awarded or not.</p> <p>CM7C: Ok.</p>	note
W2, 789-805	<p>CM7A: Yeah. Ok. Thank you, doctor sec3. So, the finally is SEARCA conclude, right?</p> <p>Sec3: No. Later, in next steps, then we will agree on what to do. We'll ask you to come up with a more...we will ask you to come up with a revised</p>	will agree, will ask, need, come back

	<p>work package proposals and come up with a better estimate of your budget...</p> <p>CM7A: Yeah.</p> <p>Sec3: ...that is needed.</p> <p>CM7A: So, uh, the last date, what you give me for the limitation for the, uh, submit this draft?</p> <p>Sec3: We'll ask CM4...</p> <p>CM7A: 17 February, you mean?</p> <p>Sec3: February 17 is the date that we submit to...</p> <p>CM7C: The date to submit of the proposal.</p> <p>CM7A: Oh. So, before that?</p> <p>Sec3: Yes, definitely before that because we need to see everything first. Because, uh, each one might be asking for two...each one might be asking for [amount in euros] times five. So, that is definitely more than what is allowed. So, we need to see it pri[or]...say, a week prior to February 17 so we can come back to you and say, oh no CM7a, you cannot get [amount in euros], only [x amount], something like that, no.</p> <p>CM7A: Yeah, ok. Ok. Thank you. Thank you.</p>	
W2, 1095-1112	<p>Sec3: Thank you very much, doctor CM5a. Yes. So, we have seen the different tasks or activities that you have proposed and, uh...Yes, doctor CM4a? (replying to a comment from chat box) Noted that they will come up with the website, not just the website but also pages, for example, in our social media available like Facebook, perhaps LinkedIn, or whatever else...</p> <p>CM5A: Or Twitter.</p> <p>Sec3: Yeah. And then, you mentioned also about the final conference, <i>no</i>?</p> <p>CM5A: Yeah.</p> <p>Sec3: That doctor CM4a also...</p> <p>CM5A: Yeah.</p> <p>Sec3: ...mentioned early on. Yes, that's why when you upload your presentations...</p> <p>CM5A: Yeah.</p>	noted, mentioned

	<p>Sec3: ...then probably later on, we can decide...</p> <p>CM5A: Yeah.</p> <p>Sec3: ...doctor CM4a whether we will transfer, uh, say the cost...</p> <p>CM5A: Yeah.</p> <p>Sec3: ...for the conference to work package five or you retain it at work package one, and so on, so that there will not be some overlaps.</p> <p>CM5A: Overlaps.</p>	
W2, 1176-1209	<p>Sec3: (pause) Yes and, uh...well, depending on our learning outcomes, I don't know, mam CM1C, are you planning to engage the industry in the design of the micro credentials?</p> <p>CM1C: That would be a good input, doc sec3, to make sure that there is an alignment. Actually, that was our rationale, <i>no</i>.</p> <p>CM5A: Yeah.</p> <p>CM1C: There is an alignment...there should be an alignment between what the industry needs and what higher education institutions should produce.</p>	make sure
W2, 1343-1380	<p>Sec3: But they need to submit like the CVs of their contact persons, the activities, the EU-funded projects that they have in the last three years, uh, as well as their annual report for the last three years, <i>no</i>, something like that. I saw that in the guidelines.</p> <p>CM4A: Ok.</p> <p>Sec3: We will inform all of the members for all of these and we will ask them to submit these at the same time that we will ask them to submit the revised work package proposals.</p> <p>CM4A: Ok. Ok. Thank you.</p> <p>Sec3: But CM4 will be like encoding all of these and uploading in the EU platform.</p> <p>CM4A: Ok.</p> <p>Sec3: Yes. For all of the five regular members who were there in the last project, as well as CM8, they all have PICs already. But, uh, I think CM9 has a PIC because they are involved in a number of other EU-funded projects. Uh, we can always</p>	need, check

	<p>check this in the registry. Sec1, could you check if CM12 and CM6 as well as Partner4 also have PICs already validated?</p> <p>Sec1: Ok po. We'll check.</p>	
<p>W2, 1397-1446</p>	<p>Sec3: Was it CM7? Ok. Yeah, because I remember I scanned the internet for those doing micro credentials and there is this Canada West Foundation. They came up with the network, uh, and they have like several recommendations for those who wish to do this. The first one being to engage the employers in the design of the micro credentials at the earliest possible stage, to link this to skills and competencies known to be in demand, and the third is to connect the micro credentials to related competency frameworks. And they mentioned that there is this climate adaptation competency framework. This is by the Adaptation Learning Network. So that the courses we will come up with in micro credentials could be like...could satisfy, or like whatever, the competency frameworks that are needed for that particular, uh, program. And then, just to mention, the fourth suggestion was to identify micro credentials that can be laddered into degree programs, like what mam CM1C mentioned, to encourage the portability of micro credentials. So that those taken from CM5, for example, can be credited towards the CM1 programs. To identify the modes of delivery, not everything need to be online. To collaborate with others to come up with an aggregate of micro credentials. To offer these micro credential learning on demand and to strengthen focus on demonstrated...I could not read my handwriting, hahaha, with micro credential assessments. To identify or develop assessment only micro credentials. Because that's one problem. I remember mam CM1C mentioned earlier that we can embed the assessment into the development of the courses, but it would be good to have a third-party assessment and that's what...that's what some institutions have for them. Like they are just on assessment only micro credentials. That's what they say. So, they have like a test that they give at the start. So, it's like a pre-test. And then, what are the gaps? Those are the ones that you need. So, enroll in this particular micro credentials and then come back again after you have passed. Then, we give you like a certificate for that particular competency or skill. But if at the outset, like if I enroll in this assessment only micro credential, for example, in food processing of whatever, if I already pass the test, I don't need to enroll in any micro credential course. They will give me already, like a certificate</p>	<p>need</p>

	<p>that I have that particular skill, something like that but, uh...and so on. I could share all of these with you because they are like nice suggestions, including the other micro credential courses that they have already instituted in their particular network. Because some of these are quite related to what we want. Uh, this is in Canada. So, I saw one by CM3, our partner there, on food and water security. They have from Royal Roads University on natural asset management and on the financial impact of climate change. Royal Roads has several micro credentials. Another one is on climate change adaptation fundamentals, intro to climate policy for climate adaptation professionals, something like that, and others. So, there is this website where they have the micro credentials being offered in that network from different universities. So, this is like a platform that we can also have for our particular project.</p>	
W2, 1447-1460	<p>CM7A: Doctor sec3?</p> <p>Sec3: Yes, CM7A.</p> <p>CM7A: Uh, may we invite CM12 to collaborate for package three?</p> <p>Sec3: Yes, by all means. I know you and doctor CM12 are best of friends, <i>no</i>.</p> <p>CM7A: (laughing)</p> <p>CM12A: Thank you.</p> <p>CM7A: Ok. Thank you.</p> <p>CM5A: Doctor sec3, I already invited SEARCA, yeah...</p> <p>Sec3: Yes.</p> <p>CM5A: ...for work package five.</p> <p>Sec3: We'll be happy...</p> <p>CM5A: Please say yes.</p> <p>Sec3: ...to work with you.</p> <p>CM5A: Ok. (laughing)</p>	invite, invited
W2, 1499-1515	<p>Sec3: Ok, uh, anything else you wish to say, doctor CM4A? Because CM4 is the project lead.</p> <p>CM4A: Ok. Yeah, nothing, just thank you very much for all the great contributions and for your time and your hard work today. So...so, we</p>	achieved, remind, need

	<p>achieved a lot of our target today. So, we work hard more and more. We hope that we could submit the application like two...like 14 is Valentine's Day in February (laughing).</p> <p>Sec3: Yes, yes. Ok. We will send you again e-mails to remind you of when to submit the next revised proposals and so on. And yes, we are also very happy because, uh, we have very good objectives, tasks, milestones, and deliverables. Better than what we did in the [MS program] because this is now really like an effort of everyone. Thank you. So, if there are no other comments, questions, inputs...Thank you very much and we hope that we will get awarded for this proposal. Of course, we need to submit first. Thank you. Sir sec2, for your final...</p> <p>Sec2: Yeah. Thank you very much for your active participation. We see all those engagement and to make more...to make our proposal more concrete, cohesive, and...we will now be finalizing it with sec3 here. We, at SEARCA, is just a facilitator. We will just be doing it for the good of all in the consortium and I'm very optimistic that we will get the proposal working and everybody will be happy. We'll get more partnership and this is really very relevant, post graduate micro credentials for...towards food security and climate change. Cheers. Thank you.</p>	
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Giving space or voice for participation. This involves actively accommodating comments, queries, and ideas from participants and making sure that each one has an opportunity to voice out any concern. Actions that reflect giving space or voice for participation include acknowledging participants who virtually raised their hand or asked for their turn to speak. This is also reflected in asking participants for any response, with long pauses to check if there are any hands raised virtually, once a topic starts or before moving on to the next topic. Some participants would also call the attention of the Secretariat when they notice another participant who would like to contribute to the discussion.

Table 5.

Giving space or voice for participation

Workshop & Line Numbers	Conversation Segment	Key Word/s
<p>W1, 224-246</p>	<p>CM4A: Yeah. As I mentioned in the [meeting] last time about the micro credential system that is offered at CM4. So, we have experiences on implementing this kind of system to the College of Integrated Science. So, I think we're ready to take on this kind of activity as a project leader. And also today, we have the Vice President for Academics, doctor CM4B at the meeting as well. I would like to invite doctor CM4B to say some few words about the readiness of CM4 to be the project leader. Doctor CM4B, yeah, please. (pause)</p> <p>Sec2: Thank you. Doctor CM4B. (pause)</p> <p>CM4B: Yes. Yes. Good morning. Yes. First of all, I would like to thank all the members that give the privilege to CM4 to be the leader of the project. I would like to say that the previous successful of [MS program] was lead by the former Vice President of CM4, which is now...he is not in the position now. So, I...I would not guarantee that it will be as good. But anyway, our team is here. So, I think we are happy and we are ready to work with all the members. I think that CM4 has the ability to be the leader of the project, yes. And as doctor CM4A mentioned, we have experience and we have already carry on module study in...we start with the School of Integrated Science and now it has expanded to other colleges, yes. So...</p>	<p>invite</p>
<p>W1, 311-329</p>	<p>CM4A: Doctor Sec2?</p> <p>Sec2: Yes?</p> <p>CM4A: Doctor Sec2...</p> <p>Sec2: Go ahead. Yes.</p> <p>CM4A: From CM4, CM4A, I would like to invite doctor CM4C. Doctor CM4C right now he is the Deputy Dean of the School of Education (inaudible), the faculty that implement micro credential system at CM4. Probably, doctor</p>	<p>invite, hear</p>

	<p>CM4C can say a few words about experience and how he handle this kind of system at UCM4.</p> <p>Sec2: Ok. Thank you. Thank you for that. We are really excited. Now, can we hear from doctor CM4C?</p> <p>CM4C: Hello. Good morning, everyone. I'm CM4C. Nice to meet you all. Long time no see. I think we... actually, we probably [met many times here]. Right now, CM4 worked in the non-degree program. I think it's similar to the micro credential program that we talked about. So, if we want to develop the like a credential program (inaudible). CM4 actually we have some experience of the non-degree program and I can share you the next occasion if you want to know.</p>	
W1, 389-402	<p>Sec1: Sir, doctor CM1D is also raising her hand.</p> <p>Sec2: Ah. Ok, mam CM1D.</p>	raising [a hand]
W1, 512-533	<p>CM7B: Doctor Sec2?</p> <p>Sec2: Yes.</p> <p>CM7B: Excuse me, doctor Sec2.</p> <p>Sec2: Doctor?</p> <p>CM7B: I'm CM7B from CM7. I'm CM7B from CM7.</p> <p>Sec2: Yeah. Ok, CM7B.</p>	excuse
W1, 569-591	<p>Sec1: Sir, I think dean CM1B is raising his hand.</p> <p>Sec2: Ok, CM1B.</p>	raising [his hand]
W1, 651-666	<p>Sec1: Sir, doctor CM1C is raising her hand.</p> <p>Sec2: Ok. Doctor CM1C.</p>	raising [her hand]
W1, 840-870	<p>Sec3: Ok. Thank you. Ok, so for Thailand, doctor CM4A, aside from CM4?</p> <p>Sec1: Mam?</p> <p>Sec3: Yes, sec1?</p> <p>Sec1: Opo, doctor CM1C is raising her hand.</p> <p>Sec3: Doctor?</p> <p>Sec1: Doctor CM1C, mam.</p>	raising [her hand]
W1, 1255-1291	<p>Sec3: Doctor CM1C, I could see your hand raised.</p>	see, raised

	CM1C: Yeah (inaudible). What about monitoring and evaluation?	
W2, 550-557	Sec3: That's [amount in euros], so yes we should be able to...procure that one. I saw some comments in the chat. Doctor CM1E is saying, (reading from screen) shall we utilize the website as our learning platform? Well, if we could have this, probably we could upload it in the...in the project's website and...but this is only to be accessed by those authorized to do so, no. It is not an open access. (Reading from screen) I am referring to the website to be developed in work package five. Yes, that's it. From Doctor CM9A of CM9, good morning. (Reading from screen) My concern is on course content, how will we deal or what kind of arrangement with our other partners from Europe or the US? Doctor CM9A, would you like to expound on your comment, please? (pause) What exactly...Yes, mam. You are on mute, mam.	[reading from screen], saw, saying, expound
W2, 877-987	Sec3: Yeah. I saw doc CM1C's hand raised... CM2B: Yeah, yeah. Sec3: ...first, so perhaps ask doctor CM1C first. CM1C: Yeah. Thank you, doctor CM2B. Yeah, I think I understand what doctor CM2B would like to install...	saw [hand raised], ask
W2, 1132-1175	Sec3: ...the project, something like that. Yes, anything else? Doctor CM4A, you want to say something? CM4A: Yeah, yeah...	[want to] say
W2, 1210-1249	Sec3: Uh, and so on. Ok. Anything else? CM7A: Doctor sec3? Sec3: CM7a, were you saying something? CM7A: Yes.	saying
W2, 1268-1276	Sec3: Yeah. Uhm, perhaps we'd like to hear from the other members who did not make a presentation. Where do you think you can come in, make a contribution? Yes, doctor CM6B? CM6B: Yes. Good morning. Sec3: Yes. CM6B: Sorry. Sec3: Yeah (inaudible), please...	hear

<p>W2, 1277-1288</p>	<p>Sec3: Ok. I believe that in some of the events, especially in the knowledge exchange events, for example, of course we can have everybody because this is like also mentoring, we get their best practices, and so on. But...but, for example, for which work package you could contribute, we'd like to hear it from you because, based on the presentations, do you think you can help develop a course on a particular topic or be part of those that will be look at university reforms, or quality assurance, and so on? (pause) We do not want to...</p> <p>CM6B: We just, uh...wait a second.</p> <p>Sec3: Sure. (pause) While you are discussing, we see president UCM12A (pause). Good morning, sir. You'd like to say something?</p> <p>CM12A: Good morning, everyone. Yup. Good morning. CM12 also would like to support, if CM4...every university would like to support, just let me know. We can support all. Yup. Thank you very much.</p>	<p>hear, see, say</p>
<p>W2, 1299-1323</p>	<p>Sec3: Yeah. So, later we will ask them who will be their representatives in this project management team, if that is how we can call it, no. Yes, uh, and anybody else who wish to say something? Otherwise, can I ask doc (pause) CM8 (pause) representative? Uh, I do not know who is here. Doctor CM8A, are you here?</p> <p>CM8A: Good morning, mam sec3.</p> <p>Sec3: Hi, sir.</p>	<p>wish [to say something]</p>

Mediating. Mediating facilitates the reaching of an agreement through finding common ground or solutions. The Secretariat does this by asking questions that guide the participants to agreeing on a task or leading a work package, among others. In a few instances where there are conflicting ideas from participants, the Secretariat mediated by putting on hold the resolution until all ideas are presented and the collective group has all the necessary information to make a decision. This prevents conflicting ideas from escalating into confrontation.

Table 6.

Mediating

Workshop & Line Numbers	Conversation Segment	Key Word/s
W1, 200-223	<p>Sec3: ...We proposed we target two of the EU priorities and that's the Green Deal, which involves climate change and digital transformation in data technologies. And our proposed project title is [MS program]. Our goal is to deliver learner-centered courses to address to address food security and climate change for lifelong learning or towards a degree. And our rationale being, that food security and climate change remain as complex challenges that we need to address innovatively, especially during this time of the pandemic. And we can elaborate on that further. For our specific objectives, we propose the following: Develop and pre-test e-module on short courses that are based on our [MS program] core courses; Institute curricular reforms for granting of micro credits and allow its accumulation towards a full course or towards a degree or certificate program; Revise university policies to enable enrollment for micro credits at any time and for students to be assessed at their own pace; and to establish a quality plan to ensure academic integrity of these micro credits courses, which may include a revision of rules on student discipline. And then for the project lead or coordinator, as has been tasked last time, SEARCA met with the CM1 chief and the dean of the graduate school. And after considering the factors for an efficient implementation of the project, we both agreed that it will be to the best interest of the consortium for CM4 to be the project lead. As has been discussed last time, CM4 has led us in the implementation of the previous [MS program] project and for which the EU has marked our project implementation as 'good'. Further, we looked into the participant registry of EU and noted that CM4 already has 18 projects funded by the EU with one serving as coordinator. This means that CM4 is familiar with the EU process of submission, reportings, and that would be to our advantage. But I leave this off for you for discussion. Thank you.</p>	met, agreed, leave [for discussion]
W1, 224-246	<p>Sec2: Thank you, sec3, for that topic on who will be on the final proposal topic and project coordinator. With this, I think we have to go to discussion for the final proposal topic and final project coordinator. We have here...and I think we have also as a promise, we will be having a talk</p>	want [to hear both from CM1 and CM4]

	<p>with the CM1 and I want to hear both from CM1 and CM4 on this one. As we move forward, we need to finalize now. May I call first, who will be represented by CM4?</p> <p>Sec 3: Doctor CM4A?</p> <p>CM4A: Yeah. Yeah. CM4A speaking. Can you hear me?</p> <p>Sec2: Yeah. We can hear you, doctor CM4A.</p>	
W1, 840-870	<p>Sec3: Yes, sir. We move to the Philippines. We only have UCM1 right now...</p> <p>CM1A: Yeah, thank you, mam sec3. I think we can include CM8, our previous collaborator for the [MS program].</p> <p>Sec3: Ok. Just CM8?</p> <p>CM1A: Yes. Thank you.</p> <p>Sec3: Ok. Thank you. Ok, so for Thailand, doctor CM4A, aside from CM4?</p> <p>Sec1: Mam?</p> <p>Sec3: Yes, sec1?</p> <p>Sec1: <i>Opo</i>, doctor CM1C is raising her hand.</p> <p>Sec3: Doctor?</p> <p>Sec1: Doctor CM1C, mam.</p> <p>Sec3: Yes, mam CM1C? (pause) Doctor CM1C? (long pause) Right. From CM4, yeah, do we have here any recommendation for another partner?</p> <p>CM4B: Yes. I think we would like to propose CM12, which is now affiliate member of the consortium. So...but we also worried a little bit about the procedure as CM2 concern because the officer approval might take time. But we do our best.</p> <p>Sec3: Thank you, mam. We believe we can help you with this because the president of CM12 is actually close to many of the consortium members. .And as you mentioned they are already affiliate member, so I believe they would be happy to be involved in the project. Can I go back to chief CM1A? I'm sorry sir to put you on the spot, but since CM12 and CM8 are made part of the project, it just...I mean, I do not know how</p>	<p>like [to propose], help, wish [to reconsider]</p>

	<p>CM9 would feel and say you're leaving us out, we're also an affiliate member of the consortium. So, chief, uh, do you wish to reconsider and bring them in also or what (laughing)?</p> <p>CM1A: Yeah, mam sec3, actually because we are also submitting for strand three and we're considering CM9 if it can consider for strand three on our own application. But, just the same, we can include CM9 because since they are already part of this consortium. So, that means we can reconsider other SUCs HEIs in the Philippines for the other strand we'll be submitting. Thank you, mam.</p> <p>Sec3: Ok. Thank you, sir. No worries, uh, the EU rules says you can be granted for at most two projects. Alright. So, we have CM8 and CM9. So, we now have three from the Philippines. And for Thailand, we have CM4 and CM12. So, we're waiting...we will be following up with CM2 for the second HEI in Malaysia. Now, do we add more partner countries?</p>	
W1, 1255-1291	<p>Sec3: Thank you. Alright. Doctor Sec2 mentioned earlier that there are six full members of the consortium and it would have been ideal for each of the full members to lead a particular work package. So, that means we have to identify at least six or six. So far, our proposal...or we have thought of four: project management and coordination, development and trainings to cover all of the development of the modules up to pre-testing, university reforms and quality plan for all the policies that we need in the university for what we want to do, communication and dissemination which is also crucial to the project and something that the EU is also closely looking at. So, if there are other work packages that you could think of, we would be happy to receive your comments, please. (long pause) Anyone?</p> <p>Sec2: Are we ok already with work package number one or these are the basic things? Of course, the project management and coordination.</p> <p>CM1C: Uhm...</p> <p>Sec2: Then, two, is project development...Ok, go ahead, CM1B.</p> <p>Sec3: CM1B...</p> <p>CM1B: Uhm, this is just a suggestion, sir sec2. For the project management and coordination, I</p>	receive, brainstorming

	<p>think CM4 can somehow decide on this because they are the one who's going to...especially for the finances. But this is just a suggestion.</p> <p>Sec2: Yeah. I think that's logical that they will be the one. So, what we could do first is add more packages before we go to the assigning. Uh, one is obvious. The coordinator will be there for one. Can you think of any other package, five, six, or are we going to merge? So, let's have a brainstorming of the different packages. Then, we'll assign, uh, volunteers or not volunteers but we have to see what are the strengths of the different universities that could lead in different packages.</p>	
<p>W1, 1322-1358</p>	<p>Sec3: CM1 lead...Would CM1 lead work package two?</p> <p>Sec2: ...big activity.</p> <p>CM1C: Ah, yeah. We are actually, uh, looking at work package five. It depends on mam CM1C and (inaudible). Would you want to lead? Actually, this is more on just facilitation, right? Not really...because everyone will be involved in this one.</p> <p>Sec2: Yeah, because CM4, CM2 will be...all the other universities will just be the coordination. Of course, SEARCA is always there in all the working packages.</p> <p>CM1C: Mam CM1D, mam UCM1C, sir, what do you think about leading package two?</p> <p>Sec3: But would you choose a package where you wish to lead?</p> <p>Sec2: Or you could choose...</p> <p>CM1C: We are actually internally talking we want package five, but, uh (laughing)...</p> <p>Sec3: Five...</p> <p>CM1D: Mam, can we clarify? Because, say for instance, in terms of the development of the module which we're talking here of each partner creating their own or maybe as collaborative online, international learning modules, right? And so, when we say leading the package, mostly the coordination of the activities of the package?</p> <p>Sec3: That's correct.</p>	<p>choose</p>

<p>W1, 1378-1425</p>	<p>CM6B: Mam sec3? Uh, I have to make a suggestion but it is difficult for me whether package three or four. So, I would like if you try to choose which package should be for CM6. Now, I will give you right to choose, what we call, you know where we are. Ok, mam sec3.</p> <p>Sec3: Ok. Let me ask the others first because they may have a preference.</p> <p>CM6B: Ok. Thank you.</p> <p>Sec3: CM5a, are you there?</p> <p>CM5A: Yeah. I'm here.</p> <p>Sec3: What about CM5? Do you have a preference? Do you have a work package you wish to lead or do you want to add another work package that you would wish to, uh, be engaged?</p>	<p>ask [others], wish, want</p>
<p>W2, 233-264</p>	<p>Sec3: Thank you, mam CM1C. We note your suggestion, <i>no</i>, and perhaps we can come back to that after we have seen the other presentations because work package three involves university policies and quality plan, so I don't know whether they included that in the quality plan component. Work package four is on the monitoring and evaluation of the micro credentials from CM2. So, I don't know again whether CM2 also considered that. So, we shall see after the presentation of these work packages, but I believe the...the quality of the implementation of the project will be covered by doctor CM4A's work package one? The implementation...the quality of the implementation of the project, <i>no</i>. Ok...</p> <p>CM1C: Thank you, doctor sec3.</p>	<p>note, come back</p>
<p>W2, 615-645</p>	<p>CM1C: Usually, for UN, usually...</p> <p>Sec3: We, like, have the venue.</p> <p>CM1C: Yeah. For UN, usually, it's hundred a day and, uh...</p> <p>CM1D: Mam, <i>hindi po</i>. It depends, like it depends on the location and then what country, what location in the country, and what month.</p> <p>CM1C: Yeah. In Laos and in Thailand, it's hundred USD a day.</p> <p>Sec2: Ah, doctor sec3?</p> <p>Sec3: Yes, sir.</p>	<p>excited, happy, hope</p>

	<p>Sec2: Thank you very much for CM1. That's a very comprehensive, uh, reporting. I'm really excited now. It's... the meat is already there. The budget is just minor. We could just massage it easily. With the UN rate, I think it's better to put it in the UN rate that we will be getting instead of CM1 rate. We would be getting more...or the SEARCA rate. We'll use that one to be more uniform for everyone and everyone will be happy for this one and I hope we'll be having face to face. Uh, yeah, I'm really excited to see all the details already there. So, we will be consolidating it and other minor workshop to make it...to firm up everything to have a more cohesive flow between the different working packages. The budget we could, uh...that would be the easy part, I hope (laughing)...</p> <p>CM1D: Ok, sir.</p> <p>Sec2: Thank you very much.</p>	
W2, 734-747	<p>Sec3: Ok. So, you can adjust the other...schedule of the other workshops from there. Ok, but we note that...doctor CM1C, the workshops that we have here clearly overlaps with some of your proposed activities for work package two.</p> <p>CM1C: Yeah.</p> <p>Sec3: Ah, yeah, I think in terms of university policies and quality plan, which is what we assigned to CM7, what can you say doctor CM1C?</p> <p>CM1C: Yeah, we could transfer the roadmap to them, maybe, and the collaboration with accrediting bodies.</p> <p>Sec3: Yes. Ok, so...</p> <p>CM1C: For standardization...</p> <p>Sec3: Yeah. And I believe this can be done simultaneously with your development of micro credential, uh, courses and so on, no? So, even without that, they can start working on the university policies to establish the system, and then the criteria, tools, and procedures for quality assurance. Ok.</p> <p>CM1C: Yes.</p>	note, say, believe
W2, 877-987	<p>Sec3: Thank you very much, doctor CM2B. Uh huh...</p> <p>CM2B: Yeah, well...</p>	heard, see, understand

	<p>Sec3: No. Yeah, well, you heard the presentation from CM7...</p> <p>CM2B: Yes.</p> <p>Sec3: ...and we see again some overlap with their proposed activities and so on. So, I do not know how to handle this. Do you have, uh...</p> <p>CM2B: Yes.</p> <p>Sec3: Do you have suggestions?</p> <p>CM2B: Yes. I think, for us, when we do this homework, we're actually looking at the monitoring, or evaluation for the whole program of micro credentials and also looking at the students, lecturers, and stakeholders, uhm, element. So, that one part and second part is the curriculum itself, the subjects or...yeah, how the modules is to be delivered. So, yeah, the two parts that to be evaluated. And then the three component is the under sustainability, so that is where the period cycle of assessment that we have to do. So, that element of evaluating also need to be discussed and produced in order to see how we can sustain this and see in the future. So, that's how we see when we do this, doctor sec3?</p> <p>Sec3: Ok. Yeah, I understand that. Uh, so, monitoring and evaluation of micro credentials versus university policies and quality plan. So, coming up with university policies on establishing micro credentials is not in your proposal, <i>no</i>?</p> <p>CM2B: No. You're right.</p> <p>Sec3: No. That definitely is under work package three. Uh, it's the quality plan in work package three that overlaps with work package four because, definitely, monitoring and evaluation is part of quality plan...hahaha. Coming up with quality assurance mechanisms, that's part of your, uh, proposed activities, doctor CM2B?</p> <p>CM2B: Yes. Maybe we'll focus on the curriculum? You...</p>	
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Highlighting a positive quality. In order to encourage participation, the Secretariat highlighted positive qualities of an institution that would make it fit

for a task or lead a work package. It is also intended to engage participants in the discussions and get their support, as observed from Sec3's statement:

And yes, we are also very happy because, uh, we have very good objectives, tasks, milestones, and deliverables. Better than what we did in the [previous project] because this is now really like an effort of everyone. Thank you.

Using affirmation in this example helps create a sense of ownership or buy-in of the collective output. This strategy is also done in order to communicate a suggestion by phrasing it affirmatively or prefacing it with a positive quality of an idea presented.

Table 7.

Highlighting a positive quality

Workshop & Line Numbers	Conversation Segment	Key Word/s
W1, 144-185	Sec3: Alright. Thank you. Thank you for the question, doctor CM7A. In fact, in the previous [meeting], there were updates about this. CM2 and CM5 are supposed to be finalizing the institution of the [MS program] in their respective universities and they are targeting the offering of the new program by the next semester. Or is it this semester? I'm not so sure now. I will have to go back to my notes. However, for the other universities, they have encountered some difficulties in instituting the program. CM1, for example, has already presented this to their GAA. It's a committee in the graduate school. However, the proposal has been sent back to the proponents for comments. At CM7, we were informed that there is like some kind of moratorium for new programs and, therefore, what you did was to offer the courses instead as part of existing programs. However, CM7 said that they hope there will come a time that the program would be instituted as one whole program. For CM4, they are supposed to be instituting. I don't know the status right now. Doctor CM4A, of what international college where this [MS program] is going to be offered? So, that's the status. It takes quite some time for the	credit

	<p>program to be officially instituted because of the processes that it had to go through. Like CM2 last time, they said it was already I believe up to the Senate but they have to go through like the Ministry or there is like an approval at the COPA. That's already ok, but they have to go through the Ministry and finally to the Senate, something like that. But the institution should be moving and, in fact, even if we have not instituted a whole program, we're expecting that at least the courses which we have already put up in detail may be offered as special topics. And we credit CM5 for already offering some of these courses in the past and we've had their reports. Thank you. I hope that answers you, Doctor CM7A.</p>	
W1, 389-402	<p>Sec2: Very good comment. Very good considerations. So, let's just put micro credits slash as we finalize later as we move on because if we will be bogged down on this one...but those are well noted. Let's just put micro credit slash micro credential, then post graduate. So, that we'll finalize it later. Thank you, CM1D, for that very insightful comment.</p>	very good, very insightful (praise)
W1, 569-591	<p>Sec2: Yeah. That's noted. We will be noting it. We will not finalize it. Any other comments? (Reading from the screen) Revise university policies influence...leverage...develop micro credentials modules...All your comments in the chat box will be noted. Any other comment regarding the third objective? Revise university policies to enable enrolments. Revise university policies to make...to make micro credit-ready universities...something like that...or micro credit-friendly universities...uhm, yeah. Any other comments on that one to make it more not like we are banging on the universities but we are working with them to make it really...I think CM1D has a very great mind in revising this one.</p> <p>UCM1D: (laughing) Sir, maybe also in terms of when you say enrolment at any time, maybe we can say flexible enrolment...</p> <p>Sec2: Yes, yeah.</p> <p>UCM1D: ...schedules. And also not to say for students to be assessed at their own pace. Maybe flexible and self-paced (laughing) enrolment because definitely even if we do self-paced there will be specific deadlines for assessments.</p> <p>Sec2: Yeah.</p>	very great mind (praise)
W1, 1359-1372	<p>Sec3: Thank you. Now to tackle policies in the university for flexible learning and the quality plan.</p>	very good

	Do we have any volunteer from the other consortium members? (pause) Sec2: Maybe CM2 is very good in that.	
W1, 1437-1447	Sec3: Alright. So, we're happy also with CM5's communication and dissemination work package, as CM5 is doing a good job with their videos, their website, and their e-newsletters every month, no? That's great. So, CM7, CM7A?	good job (praise)
W2, 202-226	Sec3: Thank you, doctor CM4A. It was a very comprehensive plan and we appreciate it very much starting from the objectives until the milestones, the deliverables, the budget...[skipped] Uh, I also find it nice that you will come up with guidelines on the financial allocation...	very comprehensive (praise), appreciate, find [it nice]
W2, 471-497	Sec3: Thank you very much, mam CM1C. Again, that was a very comprehensive list of objectives, activities, milestones, and deliverables. Uh, and we appreciate all of these. (pause) Mam, I have a question. Uh, in your...in your activities and milestones, for example you started with identifying the module writers and... CM1C: Yes, mam.	very comprehensive (praise), appreciate
W2, 1132-1175	CM5A: Yeah. I think, uh, we just received the...I mean we received the, let's say, final...final course materials, yeah, yeah? Then, again, we can discuss what kind of the, again, the platform, yeah? So, in our experience last year, we used LMS, of course, at our university...other students just enroll it to our LMS, yeah. And then, yeah, they register blah, blah, blah. It's normal and then, we received the materials from each courses, yeah. And then, yeah, I think staff cost will be there, calculated. Doctor sec3, yeah, staff cost to develop the learning materials will be calculated through the different...I think, maybe, work package two, yeah, work package two will be...and after, I mean verified by the quality work package, I think, quality work package then go to the system. And then if the community of practice can be, I don't know what kind of platform there can be also established and lot of members, for example, students, yeah, not only from the region but from other part will be great, yeah. So, this is also related to the, uh, sustainability of the...it need more...to me, it needs more discussion, yeah, by all the, all the...if our courses, my thinking is our courses are really, really good. And again, partnering with industry, I think, when developing the courses...at that time, in our micro credential courses last year, so the industry should be there. So, without industry, we cannot get the, let's say,	really good [complement]

	<p>support, yeah. So, I managed to invite speaker from the real industry, yeah, and combining, yeah. I think CM7 doing the...did the same, yeah, with different kinds of courses. So, we can...if our courses are really good, yeah, and again, whether we could in the future establish a kind of...develop a kind of knowledge management system, yeah. Again I, SEARCA, I think is really good in knowledge management. SEAMEO group, yeah, I think. Why not for the future some courses are to be charged, yeah? After...post project, I mean, yeah, post project. It's really good...to be submitting, if they want to get a credential. If they just attend, it's fine, yeah. Maybe free, but if they need this micro credential there will be cost associated for that one, yeah. So, yeah, that's my thinking, doctor CM4A.</p>	
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Using indirect language. Similar to highlighting a positive quality, using indirect language is also done to communicate suggestions. Using indirect language is demonstrated by phrasing ideas, suggestions, or recommendations as optional or as matters for consideration by using words like ‘maybe’, ‘perhaps’, ‘hopefully’, ‘something like that’, and the like, instead of directly stating a recommended action. This allows voicing out a different viewpoint without being confrontational. Using indirect language also allows participants and the Secretariat to express suggestions or ideas that they are not sure of.

Table 8.

Using indirect language

Workshop & Line Numbers	Conversation Segment	Key Word/s
W1, 389-402	<p>CM1D: Good morning, sir sec2. Just to also kind of uhm clarify on the title. I think if we are talking about certification of learning outcomes that will come out of these short courses then the proper term to use is micro credential. Since these are sub-degrees basically, they might be part of sub-degrees or that they can be ladderized to sub-degrees. Then, we should use micro credential rather than micro credit. And then I think also dean CM1B was</p>	<p>[kind of] clarify, maybe, if [we are talking about...]</p>

	<p>suggesting something like micro credential system for modular learning. If...the intention is also to take modules in [MS program]. And maybe, sir, another suggestion would be really to add post graduate micro credential, so that it's clear that we are aligning towards graduate education rather than the undergraduate if that is the intention. Thank you, sir.</p>	
W1, 623-646	<p>Sec3: You see student dishonesty, cheating in assessment, <i>no</i>? So that's why this may involve the development of new assessment tools. Plus, they mentioned at CM3 they instituted like student disciplinary action policies. I could not remember exactly now how, how they did that but towards...that's why integrity of the delivery of the course.</p> <p>CM1D: Ok. Maybe we can align in the objective towards that, mam sec3. So that it's clear that what we want to do here is to establish some form of implementation plan rather than the quality plan.</p> <p>Sec3: Ok.</p> <p>CM1D: So, whether it is, you know, creating a platform for the delivery of these...a platform and a framework for the delivery of the e-modules, maybe? But not necessarily...because, uhm I think in terms of the academic integrity of the micro credential there should also be some form of a discussion on the assessment in the development of the module.</p> <p>Sec3: Yeah. That should be part of the development...</p> <p>CM1D: Thank you.</p> <p>Sec3: ...of the module, the assessment?</p> <p>CM1D: Yes. Yes, mam. Thank you.</p>	[maybe] align
W1, 1378-1425	<p>CM6B: Mam sec3? Uh, I have to make a suggestion but it is difficult for me whether package three or four. So, I would like if you try to choose which package should be for CM6. Now, I will give you right to choose, what we call, you know where we are. Ok, mam sec3.</p> <p>Sec3: Ok. Let me ask the others first because they may have a preference.</p>	<p>make [a suggestion], give [right to choose], try [to choose], [if possible] join, [maybe] set up, [maybe] discuss</p>

	<p>CM6B: Ok. Thank you.</p> <p>Sec3: CM5a, are you there?</p> <p>CM5A: Yeah. I'm here.</p> <p>Sec3: What about CM5? Do you have a preference? Do you have a work package you wish to lead or do you want to add another work package that you would wish to, uh, be engaged?</p> <p>CM5A: Yeah, uh, since there are three and four still empty, if possible we would join the work package number four as lead. Yeah. So, this may be after we get some results, then we can conduct some dissemination and communication through...Maybe we'll set up again, as usual, website. Yeah, and social media as well. And also dissemination is good, I think. It should be done, I think, within the country. Yeah. If I'm not mistaken, the dissemination. But we will prepare...Or within the region. Yeah. I think, yeah. I think that's number work package four. Yeah. Mam sec3, I'm thinking about the sustainability, whether it could be classified as work package six or not or I just mentioned an idea. Thank you.</p> <p>Sec3: Ok. Thank you, CM5A. Dean CM2A, in monitoring and evaluation, do you take care of sustainability?</p> <p>CM2A: Uh, we can.</p>	
W2, 233-264	<p>Sec3: Thank you, sir. I see doctor CM1C, yes mam.</p> <p>CM1C: Yeah, good morning! Good morning, sir. Good morning, doctor CM4A, doctor sec3.</p> <p>CM4A: Good morning.</p> <p>CM1C: Yeah, maybe we can also include quality assurance for the outputs, doctor CM4a, cause it's the project management, uh, function to look at the quality of the outputs.</p> <p>CM4A: Uh, thank you very much. You mean the quality assurance for the project or for the module that we develop?</p> <p>CM1C: For the modules, for the...most likely for the modules. It's like the outputs.</p> <p>CM4A: I think probably...</p>	[maybe] include, [not] sure

	<p>CM1C: Just to have maybe another set of eyes to look at the output in its totality from a user's perspective rather than the developers. Even if we are going to the pre-test, it would also be, uh, incumbent upon management office to make sure, being the principal, make sure that the outputs are acceptable, outputs are of high quality...</p> <p>CM4A: I'm not sure that that could be the deliverable of the work package three or the work package two? Yeah, because the work package one is just overall. We will not touch into very specific deliverable...</p> <p>CM1C: Ok...</p> <p>CM4A: So, for the quality assurance could be at work package three or work package two. Yeah.</p> <p>CM1C: Yeah, well I was just thinking there should be another pair of eyes who will vet on the outputs because we are already doing package two. So, of course, if we are going to do it, then we'll say it's good...</p> <p>CM4A: Ok...</p> <p>CM1C: Then there's another pair of eyes who will vet on it and that could be better.</p> <p>CM4A: Ok. Yeah, I understand. Thank you very much.</p>	
W2, 1132-1175	<p>Sec3: ...the project, something like that. Yes, anything else? Doctor CM4A, you want to say something?</p> <p>CM4A: Yeah, yeah. Thank you very much, doctor CM5A, for your presentation. Uhm, I just think about something about course delivery or the platform for delivery of the micro credential. I don't know, have you...have you looked at the way that we can deliver the courses or how can we develop the platform for the achievement of the delivery of the micro credentials? Probably, we can include in your work package.</p> <p>CM5A: Yeah. I think, uh, we just received the...I mean we received the, let's say, final...final course materials, yeah, yeah? Then, again, we can discuss what kind of the, again, the platform, yeah? So, in our</p>	[probably] include

	<p>experience last year, we used LMS, of course, at our university...other students just enroll it to our LMS, yeah. And then, yeah, they register blah, blah, blah. It's normal and then, we received the materials from each courses, yeah. And then, yeah, I think staff cost will be there, calculated. Doctor sec3, yeah, staff cost to develop the learning materials will be calculated through the different...I think, maybe, work package two, yeah, work package two will be...and after, I mean verified by the quality work package, I think, quality work package then go to the system. And then if the community of practice can be, I don't know what kind of platform there can be also established and lot of members, for example, students, yeah, not only from the region but from other part will be great, yeah. So, this is also related to the, uh, sustainability of the...it need more...to me, it needs more discussion, yeah, by all the, all the...if our courses, my thinking is our courses are really, really good. And again, partnering with industry, I think, when developing the courses...at that time, in our micro credential courses last year, so the industry should be there. So, without industry, we cannot get the, let's say, support, yeah. So, I managed to invite speaker from the real industry, yeah, and combining, yeah. I think CM7 doing the...did the same, yeah, with different kinds of courses. So, we can...if our courses are really good, yeah, and again, whether we could in the future establish a kind of...develop a kind of knowledge management system, yeah. Again I, SEARCA, I think is really good in knowledge management. SEAMEO group, yeah, I think. Why not for the future some courses are to be charged, yeah? After...post project, I mean, yeah, post project. It's really good...to be submitting, if they want to get a credential. If they just attend, it's fine, yeah. Maybe free, but if they need this micro credential there will be cost associated for that one, yeah. So, yeah, that's my thinking, doctor CM4A.</p>	
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Recalling past experience. Another observation from the data is how past experience in collaboration is used as reference in the discussions. These previous experiences helped in preparing for possible scenarios or in improving

on past actions. They also provided guidance by showing how similar undertakings were resolved in the past.

Table 9.

Recalling past experience

Workshop & Line Numbers	Conversation Segment	Key Word/s
W1, 905-917	<p>Sec2: So, who were our partners from the [EU] before?</p> <p>Sec3: CM13 in Germany.</p> <p>Sec2: And we have the Austria something, Partner1.</p> <p>Sec3: Partner1, yeah.</p> <p>Sec2: So, we have to put those traditional partners because we have already some engagement and we have some experience with them.</p>	before, traditional, experience, last
W2, 202-226	<p>Sec3: ...Uhm, you mentioned that this depends upon, of course, the EU guidelines and I would just like to share that the last time that we had [MS program]. So, this was approved...I mean the start of the project was October 2016 and in February 2017 EU called for a meeting in Brussels, uh, where all the awardees or all the [EU] projects awarded during that time were invited for orientation on the implementation of the project grant, including the financial rules and so on. So, this would probably happen again today. Although, it was more for an orientation of the EU guidelines. It was also meant to network with other award recipients of [EU]. So, that would be good. And last time, they funded two participants from the project. Ok. So, I believe it will be after this that we can come up with guidelines for financial allocation and others.</p>	share
W2, 603-614	<p>CM1D: Mam sec3? Just to clarify on the budget, regarding say for instance the...because right now, CM1 has only expenses of CM1. But when we create...when we finalize the work package, this should include also, say for instance, travel of personnel from other universities, right?</p> <p>Sec3: Yes. So, I saw in the activities presented by doctor CM1C that there will be face to face workshops and so we will have to come up with travel, uh, accommodation...</p>	did [in the past]

	<p>CM1D: Accommodation. Yes...allowances, mam.</p> <p>Sec3: And so on, yeah. So, what we did in the past...</p> <p>CM1D: Hopefully...</p> <p>Sec3: Yeah. What we did in the previous project was, for example, for each activity we have an Excel worksheet and we enumerate each university partner and say two representatives from CM4, two from CM1, and so on. And then, we estimate the travel and the cost of stay to come up with an estimate for that activity. So, you do that for every activity.</p>	
W2, 713-736	<p>Sec3: And based on the last project, which has the same timeline, we submitted the proposal in February, we actually knew about the awarding very late August or already early September. But the effectivity, the implementation of the project started on October 15. So, we expect...Oh, sorry, October 16. So, we expect that this one will start...</p> <p>CM7C: Ok.</p> <p>Sec3: ...if we're awarded, and we hope that we'll...</p> <p>CM7C: In this year?</p> <p>Sec3: On October 16 of 2022.</p> <p>CM7C: Ok.</p>	knew, expect
W2, 1118-1132	<p>Sec3: ...or whatever. Yes. (pause) Uhm, I was about to say something, but I forgot. Yes. What about...I remember that last time for the [MS program], we had like a contest for coming up with a logo for the [MS program]?</p> <p>CM5A: Yeah.</p> <p>Sec3: And somebody from CM5 designed the winning logo. And doctor CM7B allocated an amount...</p> <p>CM5A: Ok.</p> <p>Sec3: ...for that. I forgot how much, but I remember doctor CM5C....</p> <p>CM5A: Ok.</p> <p>Sec3: ...was the one who received the award on behalf of the student in one of the meetings.</p>	remember

	<p>CM5A: Yeah.</p> <p>Sec3: So, perhaps...that's also for visibility, for branding, <i>no...</i></p> <p>CM5A: Yeah.</p> <p>Sec3: Logo for...</p> <p>CM5A: Yeah, yeah.</p> <p>Sec3: ...the project, something like that. Yes, anything else? Doctor UCM4a, you want to say something?</p>	
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Offering a solution or alternative. This suggests initial preparations done by the Secretariat to address possible questions or challenges from the workshops. Offering a solution or alternative helped ease participants into arriving at a decision by reducing the guesswork instead of starting from scratch. Participants also offered solutions or alternatives based on individual or institutional experiences in collaboration.

Table 10.

Offering a solution or alternative

Workshop & Line Numbers	Conversation Segment	Key Word/s
W1, 905-917	Sec3: Yes. I also endorse the inclusion of CM13. It being an affiliate member of the consortium. They really wish to participate in our activities, except that, uh, they have to source out funding for their participation. And that is why in the last [MS program], they were active in the activities. So, there were a number of activities in the region where UCM13 staff participated. So, country one, Germany with CM13. (pause) Country two, are we looking at Partner1 of Austria?.	endorse
W1, 1255-1291	Sec3: Thank you. Alright. Doctor Sec2 mentioned earlier that there are six full members of the consortium and it would have been ideal for each of the full members to lead a particular work package. So, that means we have to identify at least six or six. So far, our proposal...or we have thought of four: project	propose/thought

	<p>management and coordination, development and trainings to cover all of the development of the modules up to pre-testing, university reforms and quality plan for all the policies that we need in the university for what we want to do, communication and dissemination which is also crucial to the project and something that the EU is also closely looking at. So, if there are other work packages that you could think of, we would be happy to receive your comments, please. (long pause) Anyone?</p>	
<p>W2, 202-226</p>	<p>Sec3: Thank you, doctor CM4A. It was a very comprehensive plan and we appreciate it very much starting from the objectives until the milestones, the deliverables, the budget. Although, as you mentioned, the budget still has to be finalized. Uhm, for some comments, of course in each of the activities mentioned, we noted that you have included all the five...no, the six consortium regular members and SEARCA. But perhaps we will need to include also our other partners, especially for example, in the kick-off, I would like to believe that you want to have all of them, no, including Partner4, and CM13, and Partner1, if they are joining us and, of course, CM8 and CM12. Uh, you answered my second question and that is on whether the meetings will be face-to-face or online. You already mentioned that some of them would probably be online. I do not know if you are planning for some face-to-face meetings. We just want to know because they will have an implication in the budget because travel from one country to another would involve budget, plus the accommodation and the (pause) others related to the stay. Uh, I also find it nice that you will come up with guidelines on the financial allocation. Uhm, you mentioned that this depends upon, of course, the EU guidelines and I would just like to share that the last time that we had [MS program]. So, this was approved...I mean the start of the project was October 2016 and in February 2017 EU called for a meeting in Brussels, uh, where all the awardees or all the [EU] projects awarded during that time were invited for orientation on the implementation of the project grant, including the financial rules and so on. So, this would probably happen again today. Although, it was more for an orientation of the EU guidelines. It was also meant to network with other award recipients of [EU]. So, that would be good. And last time, they funded two participants from the project. Ok. So, I believe it will be after this that we can come up with guidelines for financial allocation and</p>	<p>[like to] believe</p>

	<p>others. Mmhmm...So, I noted the different milestones and deliverables. And as you mentioned, 1.3 which is on websites may overlap with work package five by CM5 on communication and dissemination. But we will probably discuss that again after we have seen CM5's presentation on work package five. So far, those are my comments. Thank you very much, doctor CM4A.</p> <p>CM4A: Thank you.</p>	
W2, 755-788	<p>Sec3: And then, as I mentioned to another inquiry last time, at the end, after we have seen the different proposed budget for all of the work packages, then we can adjust, like if the aggregate amount is more than [amount in dollars]...uh, euros, then definitely we will have to reduce some of the cost. But if we find that it is too small, no, that the aggregate is just [amount in euros], we can probably advise some of you to put in more in some of the items. But right now, we have not seen the total...I mean, even the final budget proposal for each of the work package. So, I suggest you just put in...</p> <p>CM7A: Yes.</p> <p>Sec3: ...how much you believe is needed for each of those activities.</p> <p>CM7A: Ok. Thank you. So...</p>	suggest
W2, 1176-1209	<p>Sec3: Yeah. It may be good to identify a few of them right now. So, we can put it into our proposal.</p> <p>CM5A: Yeah.</p> <p>Sec3: But of course, in the implementation, we can invite others.</p> <p>CM5A: Yeah, yeah.</p> <p>Sec3: Just to show...</p> <p>CM5A: Yeah.</p> <p>Sec3: ...in our proposal that where is this proof from the industry that we will be consulting.</p> <p>CM5A: Yeah.</p> <p>Sec3: Ok. Uh, and yes it will be good to consult them at the earliest possible stage, <i>no</i>...</p> <p>CM5A: Yeah.</p>	invite

	<p>Sec3: ...uh, before developing the micro credentials.</p> <p>CM5A: Yeah.</p> <p>Sec3: Perhaps in Thailand?</p> <p>CM5A: Yeah.(laughing)</p> <p>CM4A: (smiling and nodding)</p>	
W2, 1210-1249	<p>CM7A: Yes. Uh (pause) I want to ask you about the, uh...the venue of our workshop. For example, in CM7 is responsible for package three and we have four workshops...and can we organize this workshop, for example, three workshops in CM7, one workshop in other university in, for example, in Thailand, could be CM4 or CM12, something like that?</p> <p>Sec3: Yes, we can do that, sir. But we are asking everyone to upload the presentations. We want to see when you intend to do the activities because there may be, for example, two events that we can do back-to-back...</p> <p>CM7A: Yeah, yeah.</p> <p>Sec3: ...if they are scheduled almost at the same time.</p> <p>CM7A: Yeah, yeah.</p> <p>Sec3: And that's also what we did last time, <i>no</i>.</p> <p>CM7A: Yeah, yeah, yeah.</p> <p>Sec3: Because if we're meeting this week and then we will meet again two weeks after for another work package, it may be good to perhaps do a back-to-back workshop, <i>no</i>.</p> <p>CM7A: Yeah, yeah.</p> <p>Sec3: So, yes, definitely. Even if you are leading the work package, you can opt to have the workshop in Thailand or anywhere else.</p>	opt
W2, 1289-1298	<p>Sec3: Thank you very much, sir. Uh, I do not know if we will come up with like a project management team, doctor CM4A? Will this just be a small team or would you like representative from all the participating universities? Uh...I do not know, but definitely, we will be disseminating the information to all the members, and whenever you feel that you would like to</p>	[would you] like

	<p>contribute...you can contribute meaningfully into a particular work package, then please, by all means we will be happy to accommodate. (pause) Yes, sir. Yes, doctor CM6B, are you...</p> <p>CM4A: Doctor sec3, I think...</p> <p>Sec3: Doctor CM4A first.</p> <p>CM4A: Yeah, yeah. I think, probably, we can set up like a committee or comprising of representatives of each university, so that we have the contact person from each university. Yeah.</p>	
W2, 1461-1474	<p>Sec3: Thank you. So, February 7, no. No...no objection. Ok. Good and then, after that, we will come back to you by February 10 for our final feedback and perhaps...Let me see my calendar, sorry. By February 14, we can have the final, final form.</p> <p>CM4A: Yeah, sec3, I would suggest that we submit the application form like probably two days before 17...oh 14, right? 14 is the deadline, right?</p> <p>Sec3: 17 is the deadline.</p> <p>CM4A: Oh, 17. Alright. Ok.</p>	suggest

Clarifying or elaborating. This intends to address uncertainties in the discussion, which is initiated by asking questions. Participants also verbally confirm when the point made is understood, signaling the Secretariat that the uncertainty has been cleared or that the explanation given is sufficient. On the other hand, echoing or adding more explanations to what has already been said also reinforces a point or suggestion. In some instances, participants would call on a colleague from the same institution to help clarify or add to a point made.

Table 11.

Clarifying or elaborating

Workshop & Line Numbers	Conversation Segment	Key Word/s
W1, 144-185	<p>CM7A: Yeah. Thank you for the invitation for this morning workshop. Regarding some...several presentation that SEARCA today...one comment that I have to give. Note that several years ago, probably two or three years ago, that the consortium made [MS program] that involved all members of SEARCA, but after that we have no action, especially CM7 regarding the [MS program]. So, this morning I would like to ask you about the progress of [MS program]. So, thank you.</p> <p>Sec2: Yeah. Ok. Thank you for that and I ask sec3, doctor sec3 to answer that before I leave my comment also.</p>	ask, note, answer
W1, 224-246	<p>CM4B: Yes. Yes. Good morning. Yes. First of all, I would like to thank all the members that give the privilege to CM4 to be the leader of the project. I would like to say that the previous successful of [MS program] was lead by the former Vice President of CM4, which is now...he is not in the position now. So, I...I would not guarantee that it will be as good. But anyway, our team is here. So, I think we are happy and we are ready to work with all the members. I think that CM4 has the ability to be the leader of the project, yes. And as doctor CM4A mentioned, we have experience and we have already carry on module study in...we start with the School of Integrated Science and now it has expanded to other colleges, yes. So...</p>	mentioned
W1, 465-479	<p>CM4B: Yes, mister chairman. Excuse me.</p> <p>Sec2: Yes, mam CM4B.</p> <p>CM4B: Before we move first, yeah, I would like to share. Because for the first objective, if we started with this core course of the [MS program], it means that our objective is leading to getting the MS. Because normally at CM4 when we do the module course we try to like...like for the previous suggestion that this micro credential is a...there must be a clear objective of the applicants who want to study micro credential whether they want to re-skill, upskill, or they want to collect credit to go to degree. So, our short course or modular course normally it should be complete in one module that if they come to study this one short course, they will start it from the very beginning as</p>	share, expressed

	<p>the basic knowledge, uh, and then...uh, up to that day they can work with that skill that they study. But if we started with like a core course, [MS program] I'm not sure that whether the...they can get any (inaudible) of studying of those course. Only if they want to go to master then they can collect, but otherwise anyone who want to study this singular course will not get any benefit of that. I don't know what is that five core course. Normally, one core course is the basic of the whole curriculum, something like that, uh, uhm...I'm not sure whether I expressed my...my idea clearly.</p>	
W1, 512-533	<p>CM7B: Ok. Thank you. Good morning, everyone. So, I just share one of the reference for the definition of micro credential in the chat box. So, you may see, uh, the definition of micro credential. So, uh, I think the doctor sec3 has shown about the core course of the [MS program]. Actually, in the micro credential, we don't need to develop the course similar or as what's in the course of the [MS program]. I mean, for example, if one core course in the [MS program] it includes at least three to five course outcomes. So, on each micro credential courses, uh, we can develop for each course outcome. So, for example, if one core course in [MS program] it includes, for example, three course outcomes, so we can separate...become three topics of the micro credential course. So, everyone, student or non-student, they can access the topic of the micro credential. And if a student want to, uh, want to get credits from the micro credential, they can ask to the study program. For example, to get the point of the credit that he or she can get from the micro credential, if not...if for the public, so they just get a new skills, new knowledge, and new experiences in the content of micro credential. So, I think we can use the core course in the [MS program] as reference to develop the micro credential project. Thank you doctor sec2.</p> <p>Sec2: Yeah. Thank you for that. Uh, you explained it well and that's why we are piloting the [MS program] on this one. Ok thank you very much.</p>	share
W1, 623-646	<p>CM1D: Sir, can I just clarify what the objective means? Are we saying that in terms of the development of the micro credentials that we want to assure the quality? Because I think that should be a part of the second objective, when we develop the system to credit the micro credential. Unless there is a different perspective that is being taken in this objective.</p> <p>Sec2: sec3?</p>	clarify

	<p>Sec3: Uh, mam CM1D, this is actually an offshoot of the feedback from doctor CM3A of CM3, where they met challenges on...this is not in the development of the modules, but rather in the delivery. Because these are online.</p> <p>CM1D: Ah, ok.</p>	
W1, 1255-1291	<p>CM1C: Yeah (inaudible). What about monitoring and evaluation?</p> <p>Sec3: Is it monitoring and evaluation of the project or the monitoring and evaluation of the course development and delivery or...Could you specify, mam? (long pause) I would like to think it's the monitoring and evaluation of the delivery of the micro credential courses, <i>no</i>?</p> <p>CM1C: <i>Opo</i>, mam.</p> <p>Sec3: Monitoring and evaluation. Ok. So, that will be different from three, uh. <i>Ano kayang...Malaki ba ang overlap nun?</i> Sorry. Sorry, I'm speaking in the vernacular.</p> <p>Sec2: MEAL.</p> <p>CM1C: Uhm, maybe not because university reforms really refer on the policies. But M and E would cater to the outputs and the basis for the impact evaluation later.</p> <p>Sec3: Ok. So, work package five on monitoring and evaluation or...just monitoring and evaluation. Ok. (long pause) Any other so that we can have six? (laughing) Of course, we do not...if it's not necessary, we do not need to have six.</p> <p>Sec2: Monitoring and evaluation, development...training materials and the curriculum is there already?</p> <p>Sec3: Yeah.</p>	specify
W1, 1378-1425	<p>CM2A: But maybe we can discuss with you further, doctor sec3, on this, on the package number five so that we know what is the exact scope that we need to focus?</p> <p>Sec3: Uh, sorry, it's on...well, it was UCM1C who first suggested this. But as I understand, it's going to be monitoring and evaluation of our outputs. So the modules, the delivery of the modules...or rather the micro credential courses, uh...</p>	understand, believe, described

	<p>CM2A: So, this would include the course assessment and so on, right? And the program evaluation and so on, right?</p> <p>Sec3: The micro credential evaluation, right. But the program evaluation should go to the project management, I believe...I mean the project evaluation, based on the proposal, will go to the project management. But the evaluation of the modules, the quality of the trainings and so on, I believe would go on to this work package five.</p> <p>CM2A: Hmm...</p> <p>Sec3: Unless you have a different idea.</p> <p>CM2A: Uhm, I think, you know, let us look into this course in terms of to crystallize so that there's no overlapping, you know. I think, you know, at one glance, actually this is fine, but when we talk about the details, then, you know, it may be good to really know the scope for each aspect, especially towards, you know, we may see at this point of time that package two and package five, yeah, there may be possible overlapping and to avoid that to occur when we do our work later.</p> <p>Sec3: That's correct. That's why when I made the presentation earlier, after the proposed work package title, I described what I expected out of that work package. Uh, yes, it might also be that in the development of the modules you already take care in the development and delivery of the micro credential courses, you may already take care of the monitoring and evaluation. But as mam CM1C mentioned, it may be nice to have a separate work package for this. Remember they also mentioned last time about external assessment, a third party assessment, and so on. So, this may be viewed in that way, but, uh...</p>	
W2, 471-497	<p>Sec3: And there is something there where you identify the micro credential courses that will be developed. I was just wondering whether the identification of the micro credential courses will come ahead of identifying the...</p> <p>CM1C: The writers...</p> <p>Sec3: ...module writers?</p> <p>CM1C: That could be also. Although, we said...because our assumption is it has to be needs-based.</p> <p>Sec3: Ah, yeah.</p>	wondering

	<p>CM1C: It has to be locally, uh, locally determined. So, we don't know which one would fit the most. Although, we have the same experience, <i>no</i>, in the Asia Pacific region. So, maybe, we were thinking of identifying the writers first before the subject because we thought that, uh, there is that doubt on coming out with what kind of subject are they going to write about. So, if we have the writers, maybe they will be able to share their thoughts on what can they be most effective in, be most able to come up with. But, if you think, we could identify the courses first and then the writers to narrow down the process, maybe that's also possible.</p> <p>Sec3: I'm just thinking about, uh (pause)...I don't know, if we ask for an identification of the writers first and then later identify the courses, we might miss out writers...just for example, in forestry or in engineering when we see later a need for these (pause) module writers. I don't know. I was just, uh...</p> <p>CM1C: Yeah, we could...we could exchange, mam sec3. Probably, the assumption is that we already have the five. So, we do not need to do needs assessment. So, therefore, we look for people who could write about the five.</p> <p>Sec3: Ok, ok.</p> <p>CM1C: Ok.</p>	
W2, 1001-1011	<p>CM2B: Ok. Thank you, doctor sec2. Before we move, may I ask about the budget part a little bit. For the financial support for third parties, uhm, can you elaborate a little bit more, so we can have an idea what we can put in that column?</p> <p>Sec3: Uh, ok, support for third parties. Examples here are scholarships. So, suppose we are now going into the pilot testing, uh, I do not know but perhaps the consortium would think that in order to come up with...because there...because this is pilot testing, there might not be a lot out there who would be interested in enrolling. So, we say that for those who would enroll, we have this incentive. Uh, it's free or something, no. So, the cost will go under contribution to third parties.</p> <p>CM2B: Ok, understood. Ok.</p>	ask, elaborate
W2, 1343-1380	<p>CM4A: Yeah...just I like to consult with you especially, sec3, about the PIC number because all the member who participate in the project will have a PIC number. So...</p> <p>Sec3: Yes.</p>	consult

	<p>CM4A: I think most of the member already have, but some I'm not sure. Probably, you can get the PIC number. And the second one is about the mandate...the mandate that we need to incorporate in the...</p> <p>CM5A: Yeah.</p> <p>CM4A: ...in the mandate form.</p>	
W2, 1461-1474	<p>Sec3: I agree with your doctor CM4a. So, we can upload it on the 15th. We can submit on the 15th. We can already upload some of the materials that we have. (long pause) Any...and doctor CM4a, I, uh, after we collate the information from the presentation today, Partner1A of Partner1 is asking for a meeting. So, I believe it would be good to have you in that meeting. We will just contact you.</p> <p>CM4A: Sure. Sure. Ok. Thank you.</p>	agree

Expressing willingness. It can be observed from the workshops that the Secretariat initiates the confirmation of commitment by emphasizing their role in the collaboration. Sec2 demonstrated this by stating:

SEARCA is here as an enabler, as a facilitator to check with you, to review with you, and give some suggestion also, as we go along.

It suggests an intention to ease participants into expressing their willingness to take part in specific tasks as well. By highlighting their role, the Secretariat meant to assure the participants of their willingness to give assistance. As the workshops entailed assignment of tasks, participants either voluntarily express their willingness or it is elicited by the Secretariat from participants to signify acceptance to participate in a task.

Table 12.

Expressing willingness

Workshop & Line Numbers	Conversation Segment	Key Word/s
W1, 26-54	Sec2: ...Of course, what we want to commit as the secretariat of the consortium and SEARCA, we will be the facilitator. We will be the enabler to make this happen because this is an activity of the consortium. Thank you and now back for agenda number one. I want to call back again sec1 to continue the discussion or the presentation of reviewing the discussion made during the consortium [meeting] related to our new proposal for the [EU] funding. Thank you. Back to you, sec1.	commit
W1, 224-246	CM4B: Yes. Yes. Good morning. Yes. First of all, I would like to thank all the members that give the privilege to CM4 to be the leader of the project. I would like to say that the previous successful of [MS program] was lead by the former Vice President of CM4, which is now...he is not in the position now. So, I...I would not guarantee that it will be as good. But anyway, our team is here. So, I think we are happy and we are ready to work with all the members. I think that CM4 has the ability to be the leader of the project, yes. And as doctor CM4A mentioned, we have experience and we have already carry on module study in...we start with the School of Integrated Science and now it has expanded to other colleges, yes. So...	happy, ready
W1, 1302-1312	Sec2: ...But of course, I've mentioned, SEARCA is here as an enabler, as a facilitator to check with you, to review with you, and give some suggestion also, as we go along. So, work package one, project management and coordination. Obviously, it will be the UCM4 who will be leading this one. UCM4, of course, SEARCA will be there. Just put UCM4, SEARCA as a partner to help develop this package...	check, review, give
W1, 1359-1372	<p>CM2A: Uhm, so who is taking package two? We were just about to...</p> <p>Sec2: CM1.</p> <p>CM2A: Oh. Package two, CM1. Package five, CM1 also?</p>	taking/take

	<p>Sec3: No.</p> <p>Sec2: Also, but if any takers...ah yeah, not yet.</p> <p>CM2A: We thought, you know, whether package two or package five. So, if UCM1 is taking package two, then we will take package five. If UCM1 will take package five, we will take package two.</p> <p>Sec3: Ok. That's good. Dean CM1B, now you have the option (laughing).</p> <p>CM1B: Yup, we go to package two, right, mam CM1D? So, CM2 can go to package five, if that's ok.</p> <p>Sec3: Ok.</p> <p>CM1B: Thank you.</p>	
W1, 1437-1447	<p>CM1D: Doctor CM7b said CM7 will contribute in WP3.</p> <p>Sec3: Ah, ok.</p>	will contribute
W1, 1526-1537	<p>Sec2: Schedule of next workshop for work packages, leaders will be presenting their proposals. Ok. Thank you very much, sec3 and the team, for your active participation. I know everyone is very passionate and they are really very itchy to start the writing and the...of the different work packages and we have now leaders to do this and, uh, I hope we could come up as we reach August...uh, August, January 31, we already ready and we will...SEARCA, we'll be knocking at your door to make this happen. Ok. Any other final comments? SEARCA will be the...we will be communicating to you to give you the summary of this meeting and we expect your team as well as the assigned team leaders, universities, then you form your own team to make this happen. Uhm, so January 31, that's it. That will be our crucial next meeting workshop. Anything, sec3?</p>	[will be] knocking, [will be] communicating
W2, 1268-1276	<p>CM6B: As I've mentioned before on chatting that CM6 agrees and support for all concerned. So, in what part we have to participate and support for each item, please inform us what we have to do to be a part of this team. Ok. Yes.</p>	agrees, support
W2, 1277-1288	<p>CM12A: Good morning, everyone. Yup. Good morning. CM12 also would like to support, if CM4...every university would like</p>	[like to / can] support

	to support, just let me know. We can support all. Yup. Thank you very much.	
W2, 1324-1342	<p>CM4A: Uh, sec3...</p> <p>CM6B: Doctor sec3...Oh, sorry. Ok. Please doctor, CM4A.</p> <p>CM4A: CM6B first. CM6B first.</p> <p>Sec3: Ok. CM6b first and then doctor CM4A.</p> <p>CM6B: Ok. Professor CM6C already decide that we will participate in package two, development and trainings. Yeah.</p> <p>Sec3: Ok.</p> <p>CM6B: Yeah.</p> <p>Sec3: Right...and do you have someone in particular whom CM1 can coordinate with for this particular work package?</p> <p>CM6B: Yeah. Yeah, meanwhile, I will be what we call the representative from CM6.</p> <p>Sec3: Ok.</p> <p>CM6B: And then we would like to make a small team to support for work package two. Yeah.</p> <p>Sec3: Alright.</p> <p>CM6B: And CM6 will provide any facility and any concern to make, what we call our proposal, as well as in order that our proposal is accepted by [EU], we will also provide for any material that written in proposal. Yeah.</p> <p>Sec3: Thank you, doctor CM6B. That's noted. Doctor CM4A?</p>	decide, provide

Verifying or reconfirming. Validating and reiterating the acceptance of a task or role ensured the certainty of participants in the decision they have made. This also established accountability from each participant as the Secretariat took note of each participants' commitment. In some instances, participants also

asked other participants to confirm their acceptance to work together on a certain task or work package.

Table 13.

Verifying or reconfirming

Workshop & Line Numbers	Conversation Segment	Key Word/s
W2, 69-98	<p>Sec3: Yes. Good morning to everyone. Let me just share my screen and this...this...Uh, ok. So, this is an update on our partner beneficiaries both from the EU and in Asia. So, last meeting as Sec1 mentioned...Why is this not moving? Ok. We have decided on the partner beneficiaries in Asia and we thank CM8, CM9, and CM12 for confirming their participation in our project. For Malaysia, we heard from CM2 that they are targeting Partner4, but we would like to get the confirmation right now, dean CM2A?</p> <p>CM2A: Yes. Yes, it is confirmed, doctor sec3.</p> <p>Sec3: Ok. Thank you very much. So, we have Partner4 joining us in the project for the second HEI from Malaysia. For partner beneficiaries in the EU, we wrote to CM13, specifically to doctor CM13A, who was also our contact during the [MS program]. She expressed interest from CM13 to be part of our project anew. In fact, she had several suggestions. She said that she is...that CM13 is part of another EU-funded project called (project1) and this is made up of nine EU universities. And they are also...part of the project is also to come up with micro credentials. So, she said that she is suggesting a knowledge exchange event on the establishment of a micro credential system, whereby these EU universities could share their experience on the matter. She is also keen on CM13 participating in the development of an online course, especially one related to forestry sector. They're also doing one right now in another project also with Indonesian partners. And she said they also want to explore the development of digital measures to facilitate international student mobilities. Though, these are going to be virtual mobilities. So, these are the</p>	get [the confirmation], confirmed, joining

	<p>suggestions that she made and she has already brought to the central administration of CM13 this proposal. In fact, she is asking for more details, but I promised to give her that after this workshop. And, uh, for PARTNER1, we contacted doctor PARTNER1A. He was very active in the [MS program]. He would also be happy for PARTNER1 to be part of the project, except that he wants to see the details of the work packages and would probably, uh, want to have a short meeting to discuss how PARTNER1 can make a meaningful contribution to the project. So, I told him again that after this meeting we will come back to him for more details. But I also informed him about the suggestions made by CM13, so he could also think of similar contributions from the side of PARTNER1. Unfortunately, doctor PARTNER1A has not yet responded to my e-mail, but I'll send him a WhatsApp message later. So, I have not...well, I have not yet contacted Partner2 because I wanted to see as an affiliate partner the contribution also that they could make after our work package details have been presented. So, on my part, that's it and, uh...Sorry. Now, sec1, perhaps we can go to the next item.</p>	
<p>W2, 1299-1323</p>	<p>Sec3: Yeah. So, later we will ask them who will be their representatives in this project management team, if that is how we can call it, no. Yes, uh, and anybody else who wish to say something? Otherwise, can I ask doc (pause) CM8 (pause) representative? Uh, I do not know who is here. Doctor CM8A, are you here?</p> <p>CM8A: Good morning, mam sec3.</p> <p>Sec3: Hi, sir.</p> <p>CM8A: Good morning, everyone. Let me check if doctor...Like the other, <i>ano po</i>, universities, who already expressed their support, so let me also confirm to you po that CM8 is supportive of this project. But let me just, uh, <i>ano po</i>...ask. Do we need to identify now which work packages are we going to participate in? Is that, uh, what we need to do now?</p> <p>Sec3: Ah, actually, it would be best if you could inform us now in which work package you would like to contribute, so that our work</p>	<p>ask, confirm, note, understand</p>

	<p>package leaders can contact you for further details. Like, for example, doctor CM1C said earlier that they will lead in the development of the micro credentials, but they're not going to do all of that, no. So, although we have not yet identified what courses, but we hope we can get other consortium members to contribute to that particular work package...and also with the others.</p> <p>CM8A: Yes. Yeah, but for CM8, can we request that we will have to consult first with our executives? But we are, <i>ano</i>...doing something equally important right now. So, can we just contact directly the work package team leaders later? But we'll just have to confer with them first. Thank you very much.</p> <p>Sec3: Yes, sir, of course. Thank you. We note the interest and, of course, we understand that you have to get clearance from higher authorities. So, yes, we will count on you sir to contribute to one or more of the work packages.</p> <p>CM8A: Yes, mam. Mam, so we can just ask you <i>po</i> for the contact information of the team leaders from you or miss sec1 after the meeting?</p> <p>Sec3: Yes, sir. Yeah.</p> <p>CM8A: Thank you very much <i>po</i>.</p>	
W2, 1475-1486	<p>Sec3: Are there any other questions, comments, or suggestions? From CM1? None, doctor CM1c?</p> <p>CM1C: None from my end.</p> <p>Sec3: Ok. So, doctor CM1C will be the main contact for CM1, <i>no</i>?</p> <p>CM1B: Yes, mam sec3. (laughing)</p> <p>Sec3: (laughing) So, the Dean says yes. Ok. Uh huh, of course we have doctor CM4A for CM4, CM5A for CM5, CM7A for CM7, and CM2B for CM2, <i>no</i>? Ok. And for CM8, we'll contact CM8A. For CM12, doctor CM12a is always there, so that's good. And for CM9, mam CM9B, will you be our main contact? (checks screen, nodding) Mam, you're on mute (pause).</p>	says, will contact, expect

	<p>CM9B: Yeah, ok, mam sec3. No problem.</p> <p>Sec3: Thank you. Thank you, mam. We will expect that you will contribute in one or more of the work packages. Thank you.</p> <p>CM9B: Ok.</p>	
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Accomplishment of IOC

The 12 communicative practices discussed in the previous section culminates into the accomplishment of IOC through the following:

Contextualizing. Three (3) communicative practices demonstrate contextualizing as an accomplishment of IOC that ensures participants have a common understanding of the collaboration, e.g. what it is about, what needs to be done, as well as putting order in the discussions. Contextualizing provides information to which the collaboration could be hinged on, and this set of information is continuously reinforced through instruction and alignment.

Consensus building. Once the collective group has established a common understanding of meanings, they are better positioned to decide on tasks or roles. Consensus building as an IOC accomplishment embodies inclusivity and avoidance of conflict in decision-making. It is important to note that consensus building practices are often observed in combination with one another in order to ease the participants into making a decision.

Confirming commitment. Given a common understanding of the collaboration and an initial consensus among participants, confirming commitment would be necessary to finalize the action to be taken. Confirming

commitment enables participants to take responsibility for specific actions needed for the collaboration to work. As in the case of the Consortium, the participants were able to regroup at another date and time to present the results of their commitment.

Communicative Constitution of IOC

The table below summarizes the 12 communicative practices according to the meta-theme they accomplish:

Table 14.

Meta-themes derived from communicative practices identified

Contextualizing	Consensus building	Confirming commitment
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Providing background information ● Giving instructions ● Aligning 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Giving space or voice for participation ● Mediating ● Highlighting a positive quality ● Offering a solution or alternative ● Clarifying or elaborating ● Recalling past experience ● Using indirect language 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Expressing willingness ● Verifying or reconfirming

Contextualizing, consensus building, and confirming commitment or the 3Cs occur interdependently. As such, the 3Cs are tied to one another, suggesting that these accomplishments of communicative practices should be used together in order to sustain interorganizational collaboration. For instance, without contextualizing the

nature of collaboration, it would be difficult to reach an agreement among different parties. If agreements are reached at all, participants could also have different interpretations of what they have committed to. On the other hand, without consensus building, decisions made might not result from a consultation with individual members but rather imposed such as in top-down decision-making. This could affect the buy-in from individual participants on the tasks that they should perform. Finally, without confirming commitment, agreements and tasks could remain unperformed. This could also result in conflict, particularly in meeting the requirements of the collaboration.

To answer how contextualizing, consensus building, and confirming commitment become constitutive of IOC, we then look into co-orientation as a key concept of CCO, whereby organizational members align their actions to common objectives through conversation and text (Taylor and Van Every, 2000 as cited in Koschmann, 2012). In particular, the explanation follows the A-B-X format adapted from Newcomb's communication model, wherein A and B represent different individuals or groups and X represents the matter of concern (Fox and Jahn, 2022).

In most instances, A would represent SEARCA as facilitator of the workshop and Consortium Secretariat, while B represents the workshop participants or the Consortium members. This, however, does not neglect that A and B could also represent different individuals or groups among the workshop participants or among the Secretariat representatives. For the purpose of discussion, the first instance will be used to demonstrate the co-orientation process.

At the level of contextualizing, co-orientation happens as A and B establish X or the common understanding of the project and its requirements. Contextualizing provides information to which the collaboration could be hinged on, and this set of

information is continuously reinforced through instruction and alignment. This forms a collective understanding among individual participants about the collaboration.

Figure 6.

Contextualizing as co-orientation

Next, co-orientation in consensus building is exhibited through negotiation of tasks and roles (i.e. X) between A and B. Through consensus building, meanings continue to be established and re-established. Once the collective group has agreed on a common understanding of meanings, they are better positioned to decide on tasks or roles.

Figure 7.

Consensus building as co-orientation

Lastly, A and B establish accountability (i.e. X) by confirming commitment, wherein willingness to participate is expressed and certainty of a decision made is reinforced. This enabled the participants to regroup at another date and time to present the results of their commitment. They were also able to follow through with the submission of their respective work packages outside of the workshops.

Figure 8.

Confirming commitment as co-orientation

As a culmination of co-orientation, authoritative text, as described by Koschmann (2009), shapes IOC in terms of defining roles and characterizing the collective organization. The 3Cs demonstrated authority through its ability to coordinate collective action through co-orientation. In doing so, the 3Cs become the authoritative text that enabled individual members to act in consonance with the collective organization.

Overall, communicative practices of the international body, through its interaction within the interorganizational network, accomplish IOC through contextualizing, consensus building, and confirming commitment. These accomplishments, in turn, constitute IOC through co-orientation and formation of authoritative text.

Chapter VI

RESEARCH SUMMARY, CONCLUSION, IMPLICATIONS, AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Summary

Interorganizational collaboration or IOC involves cooperative relationships that share resources toward a common objective. Globally, IOCs remain relevant in order to address the growing complexities of issues and demands from different sectors of society. Providing an explanation of IOCs through a communication lens helps broaden understanding of such complexities and gives basis to assessments of communication issues that may arise in IOCs, among others.

This study looked into the communicative practices of a consortium, formed through an international treaty organization, to understand how these practices accomplish IOC. This is in line with the Montreal School of the communicative constitution of organization or CCO approach, wherein conversations reflect the collective experience of individual members and becomes authored into text that shapes the collective organization. Using the ethnomethodological tradition, audio and video recordings from Consortium workshops were transcribed and analyzed into common themes.

Twelve communicative practices were identified and were further categorized as contextualizing, consensus building, and confirming commitment or the 3Cs. Contextualizing establishes a common understanding among collaboration participants. Consensus building is done toward making inclusive agreements, avoiding any conflicts as much as possible. Lastly, confirming commitment ensures accountability for actions that sustain the collaboration.

Conclusion

Communicative practices of the international body, through its interaction within the interorganizational network accomplish IOC through contextualizing, consensus building, and confirming commitment. These accomplishments, in turn, constitute IOC through co-orientation and formation of authoritative text. The 3Cs are co-orienting practices, in that they enabled members of the international body to align their actions toward common objectives. These co-orientation practices culminated in the formation of authoritative text, which is demonstrated through the collective action as it reflects agency given to the abstracted text formed through the 3Cs.

Implications

This explanation of IOC through the 3Cs could help gain a better appreciation for communication, which goes beyond message transmission. It reinforces the notion that communication is a foundation for IOC. The identification of the 3Cs as communicative practices that accomplish IOC further places communication as constitutive of the organization. More specifically, the 3Cs demonstrate how IOC among Southeast Asian organizations is accomplished through co-orientation practices.

The 3Cs provide additional insight as to what makes the Consortium distinctive as an IOC through a collective identity. They suggest that the collective organization operates on establishing a common understanding, diplomacy, and accountability to accomplish interorganizational collaboration. Koschmann (2012) argued in his study on 'The Communicative Constitution of Collective Identity in Interorganizational Collaboration' that collective identity itself is an authoritative text that 'induce action and coordinate the activities of diverse stakeholders'.

Contextualizing the collaboration lays the groundwork for consensus building, which is a hallmark of Southeast Asian foreign relations or what has been called the 'ASEAN way'. The 'ASEAN way' has been characterized by non-confrontational practices, maintaining independence among the member countries, peaceful resolution of conflicts (Villanueva and Manalo, 2017) and its 'procedural use of consensus building' (Narine, 1998; Yzawa, 2006; von Feigenblatt, 2011). For consensus to become functional, or in this case result to collective action, Villanueva further suggests that forms of accountability need to be included at different levels of regional governance. Confirmation of commitment in an IOC demonstrates accountability and gives individual members a sense of ownership (Koschmann and Isbell, 2009).

Recommendations

This study offers a unique point of view of IOC on an international context and also gives insight into Southeast Asian collaboration. Future research may also look into Southeast Asian collaboration in other thematic areas and consider other forms of collaboration like joint programs and mergers, among others. This could contribute to the growth of IOC literature in the international context.

Future research may also consider the Southeast Asian experience in IOC in terms of its collective identity as authoritative text. While studying a consortium that has been in existence for many years proved to be beneficial in providing a rich context, it could also be of interest to future researchers to study IOCs in their initial stages to better appreciate the role of communication in the formation of an emerging collective identity.

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